

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan (for START)
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KoM	Kick-off meeting
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy
TEG	ThermoElectric Generators
MTOD	Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication” in the period 1st December 2023 – 31st May 2024¹ (M19-M24 of the START project).

It covers the endeavours within the following tasks (the ones running in said period):

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.4: Clustering

Task 6.3 (Training) is also running, but it is being reported in D6.8 also in May 2024 (M24), so it is not touched upon here if not to mention some activities that can also be considered as Dissemination.

The activities for D&C, that are reported in this deliverable, include:

- Updates to the START project website.
- Updates to the START DCP.
- Updates on the Social Media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter, Twitch, SlideShare).
- The fourth issue of the public biannual newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE”.
- The fourth free webinar, and the upcoming hybrid fifth webinar.
- Publications (an article on the website Innovations News Network).
- Dissemination at events (workshops, congresses and others, in person and online), including some upcoming training events (EPMA Summer Schools, training webinar).

The KPIs set for the D&C activities have been met (not considering those that have a longer deadline), with the exception of Twitter/X, but some data reassure on a positive impact even on that platform and the reviewed KPI is attainable.

The clustering activity has continued in such a way that the database on EU-funded projects, which was created at the beginning of the project, has been further updated and completed. Contacts led to START project joining an existing project clustering initiative (ERHASE) and planning to cluster with the project THERMOS and other newly started projects.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to month of May 2024 could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same series, D6.9 (M30, November 2024).

4 INTRODUCTION: STRUCTURE OF WP6 AND GENERAL PLAN OF ACTIVITIES

4.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project in order to maximise its impact. The key objectives are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites and social media
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

All partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

4.2 STRUCTURE OF WP6

4.2.1 Tasks

The activity is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT shows that only Tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 have already begun, whereas Task 6.5 will only run in Year 4.

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026. Bordered in orange, the period covered by this deliverable D6.7 (M19-M24).

4.2.2 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP lists 15 deliverables out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022). The deliverables (all classified as public), also visible in Figure 3, can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed. *(D6.3 and D6.4 submitted and approved, D6.6 submitted, D6.7 is the present report, D6.9 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented. *(D6.5 submitted and approved, D6.8 being submitted in May 2024)*
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

Concerning milestones, only one was envisaged, namely Milestone 08:

- MS08: Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible

The website was in fact the key stone of all further dissemination, so it needed to be started as early as possible and was set as a milestone. This milestone has been achieved as planned (declared on 22 August 2022 on the Funding & Tenders Portal, the website being also subject of Deliverable D6.1 submitted earlier and already accepted).

Deliverables												
Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status
WP6	D6.1	D19	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6.	EPMA	DEC	PU	31 Jul 2022		29 Jul 2022	31 Aug 2022	Approved
WP6	D6.2	D20	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities.	EPMA	R	PU	31 Aug 2022		30 Aug 2022	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.3	D21	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M6	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2022		30 Nov 2022	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.4	D22	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.5	D23	Training activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.6	D24	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M18	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2023		30 Nov 2023		Submitted
WP6	D6.7	D25	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.8	D26	Training activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.9	D27	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M30	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.10	D28	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.11	D29	Training activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.12	D30	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M42	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.13	D31	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.14	D32	Training activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.15	D33	Final Event	Final event conference report.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 Mar 2026				Pending

	To be completed on the current year
	Deadline approaching
	Submitted
	Approved

Figure 2: List of WP6 deliverables, with deadlines and status.

5 TASK 6.1: SPECIFIC PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

The objective of this task is to develop tools and produce materials that will be used during and after the project to disseminate the information about the project, its partners, and its results. According to our proposal, these were the items that needed to be developed:

- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) at the start of the project (described in full in Deliverable D6.2 submitted in August 2022) and updated when required (a mid-term update by M24 was made, another one will be made at M48).
- Described in Deliverable D6.1 (submitted in July 2022):
 - The Project's Graphical Identity (logo, branding).
 - The START project website.
 - A special area on the EPMA website (www.epma.com) devoted to the START project.
 - Social Media platforms, in particular:
 - A LinkedIn page for networking with the professional community (managed by EPMA).
 - A YouTube profile for engaging with the greater public (managed by EPMA).
 - A Twitter/X account for business and policy makers (managed by LPRC).
 - A Twitch profile for engagement with young people (managed by LPRC).
 - A SlideShare account for disseminating project presentations globally (managed by ASGMI).
- Leaflets, posters, banners, branded consumables that will be used as advertising material to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A public biannual newsletter to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A serious game (see WP7, Task 7.1 and deliverable D7.2)
- Videos about the project (2 generic videos, 1 at the start and one at the end, 3 more focused videos on specific topics).

The tools had been further described in the original proposal as in Table 1.

Table 1: Tools for Dissemination and Communication as indicated in the proposal.

Tool	Purpose	Audience	Due	Quantified target
Project Graphical Identity	A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.	All	M02	-
Project website	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content, including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.	All groups	M02 onwards	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4
Social media	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.	All groups	M02 onwards	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project ² LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.
Videos	Some videos are planned for various uses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used for general awareness about START. • A mid-term longer video, highlighting preliminary project results. • 2 or more short videos focused on different subtopics within the project, with examples of improvements achieved within the project. • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used as a summary of the results obtained in START. 	Groups 1-4 1-3 2-3 1-4	M04 M24 M48 M48	Average of 200 views per video (at least 100 total views)
Newsletters	A public biannual newsletter will be circulated to individuals who sign up. The newsletter will include a summary of the activities over a 6-month period.	Groups 1-3	M06 onwards	Demand led but minimum of 500 per semester
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Communication of the project outcomes and activities, to share knowledge, ideas and updates.	Groups 2, 3	M06 onwards	Audience of 100 per event
Serious online game	A serious online game for capacity building on raw materials, sustainability and circular economy.	All groups	M24 onwards	Visitors: 300
Other publications	Articles on web-based innovation news services, like the Horizon Magazine, Cordis, and on commercial magazines like Open Access Management	All groups	M06 onwards	Total reach >400000

New achievements will be described in the next pages.

5.1 UPDATE OF THE DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

As mentioned, the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) was compiled at the start of the project, described in full in Deliverable D6.2 submitted in August 2022, and it must be updated when required. As a general prescription, an update was considered by M24, mid-term, that means at this point of the project. Consequently, the update has been made and it is stored on the project's SharePoint.

The main changes are:

- A postponement of one of the videos from M24 to M30
- The organization of an industrial workshop around M28

² The Twitter/X KPIs have been reviewed, see 5.8.1.2.

- The change of Twitter/X KPI from Followers to Impressions (15k/year in Year4).

5.2 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project's website has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. It also constituted the criterion for the achievement of Milestone MS08 ("Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible"), that was declared achieved on 22nd August 2022.

The website address is:

www.START-HEproject.com

Another site address, www.HE-START.eu, is automatically redirected to the main address.

The website is continually updated in terms of contents and new features are introduced (new pages, widgets, etc.) if deemed useful.

During the last six months, the period covered by this deliverable, there were no changes in the structure of the website, but some news items, media and documents were added.

On the "Documents" page, only one document was added, i.e. the fourth issue of the Newsletter, published in April 2024 (Figure 4). More documents will be made available in the future as some publications are being prepared.

The "News" page is the first place where the info about the events and the news about the project are posted (Figure 5). The news published amount now to 25, as we published 5 in the last 6 months:

1. Launch of the InComEss Final Workshop
2. Launch of the START Webinar #4
3. The publication of an article on Innovation News Network
4. The footage of the START Webinar #4
5. The publication of Newsletter RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue #4

In the Multimedia page (Figure 6), 1 more item is now available, that is the footage of our Webinar #4, held In March 2024.

The "Consortium" page had to be updated due to the change of logo by the partner 3drivers (Figure 7). The logo carousel in the Home page was consequently updated too.

Figure 4: Updated Documents page (screenshot taken on 10/05/2024).

Figure 5: The updated News page (screenshot taken on 10/05/2024).

Figure 6: The updated Multimedia page.

Home The Project Documents News Multimedia Consortium CONTACT

Laboratorio Nacional de Energia e Geologia I.P. (PT) - Coordinator	https://www.lneg.pt/
3 Drivers - Engenharia, Inovação E Ambiente Lda (PT)	https://www.3drivers.pt/
Asociacion De Servicios De Geologia Y Minería Iberoamericanos (ES)	https://asgmi.org/
Bundesanstalt Für Geowissenschaften Und Rohstoffe (DE)	https://www.bgr.bund.de/
European Powder Metallurgy Association AISBL (BE)	https://www.epma.com/
GeniCore Sp. Z. o.o. (PL)	https://genicore.eu/
Geo Unterweissacher GmbH (AT)	https://www.geo-unterweissacher.at/
Geosphere Austria (AT)	https://www.geologie.ac.at/
La Palma Research Centre SL (ES)	https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/
MBN Nanomaterialia Spa (IT)	https://www.mbn.it/
RGS Development BV (NL)	https://www.rgsdevelopment.nl/
Statny Geologicky Ustav Dionyza Stura (SK)	https://www.geology.sk/
Sintef AS (NO)	https://www.sintef.no/
TEGnology ApS (DK)	https://www.tegnology.dk/
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Científicas (ES)	https://www.csic.es/

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Figure 7: The updated Consortium page.

5.3 EPMA NEWSLETTERS

EPMA publishes regular newsletters for its members and for interested contacts. These are containing at least the link to the START website (typically in the weekly E-Mail newsletters distributed to more than 1600 member contacts and in a reduced version to 400+ non-member

contacts), if not specific pieces of news. The latter case happened with two weekly newsletters at the beginning of December 2023, when the Issue #3 of the START Newsletter was advertised (Figure 8) and linked, and with one periodic (quarterly) EPMA Newsletter issue. Figure 9 shows the text included in EPMA's quarterly newsletter #130, published in March 2024. This latter publication is now web based³, not sent via E-Mail as in the past.

³ <https://www.epma.com/epma-newsletter-130/>

Figure 8: Content of two EPMA weekly newsletters, including the news of the launch of Issue #3 of the START Newsletter: (left) 5th December 2023 edition; (right) 12th December 2023 edition. All weekly newsletters also contain the usual link to the project website.

European Projects

START is making progress towards new thermoelectric devices

The Horizon Europe project START ("Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste

recycling"), dealing with thermoelectric materials made from mine waste minerals (sulphides like the tetrahedrites) and to be used in waste heat recovery devices, has continued this year, and many results will soon be available on the materials developed.

EPMA is mainly involved in the dissemination of the outcomes of the project, and is currently active both in preparing new materials and new events.

A new issue of the "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE" newsletter is being prepared, and it will be the 4th issue. If you have missed any previous issues, you can find them all on the project website.

START will be present in a booth organised by the funding agency HaDEA at the world geology exhibition PDAC 2024; then later a presentation will be given during the EPMA General Assembly in May. In early June, the consortium will meet in Oslo for the annual assembly, and in July, a demonstration concerning thermoelectric devices is being prepared, to be given to the participants of the EPMA Summer School in Alessandria, in July.

START is also liaising with other projects and took part in the final workshop of the InComEss project, as a part of the ERHASE cluster dedicated to energy harvesting, on 31st January; and will liaise now with the EraNet project THERMOS led by TU Dresden.

But the closest interesting activity is the 4th free webinar, that will be held on 14th March, and that will focus on the powder metallurgical processing of thermoelectric materials, and their assessment. The presenters are Serena Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia), Damian Karpowicz (GeniCore) and Patricia Almeida Carvalho (Sintef). It will be

possible to register until the start of the webinar, so everyone is invited to join: please refer to the website or the LinkedIn advertisement.

If you are interested in the project, check out its website www.START-HEproject.com, and find out more; you can follow also on X, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc. Subscribing to the mailing list on the website will allow to directly receive news about the project, and in particular the newsletter.

Figure 9: EPMA Newsletter #130, March 2024.

5.4 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media are the tool used by the project to engage the audience, bring them to the website, and in general to disseminate and communicate (also to the wider public) about START activities, results and partners.

The project's social media accounts have been already created and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. The START social media are:

- Twitter/X (partner responsible: LPRC): https://twitter.com/START_HEproject
- LinkedIn (EPMA): <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>
- YouTube (EPMA): <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2lnPA>
- Twitch (LPRC): https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project
- SlideShare (ASGMI): <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

In addition to these, an account on the Zenodo service⁴, the Open Data service created by CERN within the OpenAIRE project in 2013, that also offers the creation of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, has been created by LNEG and is used, in parallel with SlideShare, to help us assuring that the rule for OpenAccess publication is fulfilled (see chapter 6.4), together with the publication on our website and social media.

5.4.1 Activity on Twitter/X

START Twitter/X posts have two main goals:

1. Sharing information with the community on the project's goals, objectives, and concept, as well as on the relevant communication activities such as presentations at conferences, the START video, the webinars, workshops and meetings, and online materials and,
2. Sharing how the START project contributes to the main topics of interest, e.g., thermoelectrics, reuse of mining waste, waste heat energy, green energy and sustainability.

During M19-M24 a total of 37 posts were made, spanning from 13/11/2023 to 02/05/2024, and contributing to the following statistics:

- 1) Total number of Followers: 192 (raising from 147 since last 6 months)
- 2) Number of views/Impressions during the period: 4714

Total number of Audience (counted as Engagements + Detail Expands + New followers + Profile visits) statistics are somewhat similar to the previous period regarding the number of posts and expected Impressions and Engagements. Where the numbers are better than expected is in the number of page followers, which raised from 147 to 192 within 6 months. This is still a somewhat low number of followers, but the statistics of Impressions and Engagements make up for it, indicating that the impact of the publications on Twitter/X is still interesting for communication purposes.

As the KPI for X has been reviewed to consider Impressions, and not Followers (see the chapter 5.1 on the update of the DCP), this is discussed in the relevant chapter below (chapter 5.8.1.2). Figure 10 shows the "homepage" of the START Twitter/X account.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

Figure 10: The START Twitter profile (status on 02/05/2024).

5.4.2 Activity on LinkedIn

The activity on LinkedIn continued along the two already established main lines:

- Achieving a larger audience for the START page. This was done mainly by EPMA, using the network available to them. At the date of 29 November 2022, the page followers were 142, on 6th May 2023 the number increased to 312, on 9th November 2023 to 408, and at the date of 26th April 2024 they are now 515.
- Posting project news to bring interest and send interested people to the website, if possible, to let them subscribe to the project's mailing list.

Occasionally, some third-party news has been published, in order to create some traffic to the page (a similar approach has been followed on Twitter).

Followers have been growing steadily, growing to more than 500 in May 2024, about 200 added in the last 12 months. It is believed that this number will further increase. The objective is to reach 800 followers by the end of the project, and, when scientific results will be shown and interesting events are organised, it will be easier to attract followers, so it is likely that the KPI can be reached, with 2 years of project duration still left.

Concerning posts, in the period between 10/11/2023 and 09/05/2024⁵ there were:

- 23 posts on the START page (almost 1 per week).
- 66 posts on LinkedIn groups ("EPMA networking group", "Sustainability professionals" group, "Thermoelectrics" group, "Thermoelectric matters" group, "Metallurgy and Materials Science" group, "Global Metallurgist, Metallurgical & Material Engineers Community" group, "Materials Research Society" group, "Materials Research Network" group, "Materials Science Engineer" Group, "American Ceramic Society" Group, "Horizon Europe, Framework Programme for Research and Innovation" Group).
- posts on personal accounts (surely more than 12, as this is the number posted by B. Vicenzi, the EPMA main contributor to LinkedIn, on his own account, that lists about 1900 followers) by members of the consortium, that have been only partly considered in the evaluation of impact, plus other posts on some partners' pages.

See also paragraph 5.8.1.1 for relevant KPIs.

5.4.3 Activity on YouTube

On YouTube the activity is lower, as it practically involves the uploading of the videos produced during the project. There are now 13 videos on the START YouTube channel, for a total of almost 7 h of video time, ranging from just above 1 m to 1 h 34 m each; and about 450 total views. Here follows an update of the data about views. All data reported here have been acquired on 26th April 2024.

5.4.3.1 START introductory video (published on 25th October 2022)

To date, visualisations on YouTube have grown to 120, with a slow growth that is still continuing.

Figure 11: Statistics for visualisations of the START introductory video on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

The analysis of visualisation did not change much from the previous assessment, behaviour shows that 31.2% of the users viewed the video beyond the 30s mark, for an average duration of the views of 27 seconds.

⁵ The previous deliverable D6.6 reported data until 9th November 2023.

Figure 12: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START introductory video (YouTube).

5.4.3.2 START Webinar #01 - 2023-28-02 (published on 6th March 2023)

After just more than one year from publications, views increased to 52 (14 in 6 months).

Figure 13: Statistics for visualisations of the START Webinar#01 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

Retention is still not high, only 6.9% of the video is normally watched, for an average duration of 4m24s.

Figure 14: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START Webinar#01 video on YouTube.

5.4.3.3 START - 8th March 2023 - Gracia Olivenza (ASGMI) (published on 8th March 2023)

This was a short video that has now 7 visualisations on YouTube (2 in the last 6 months). No significant statistics in this case.

5.4.3.4 START - 8th March 2023 - Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC) (published on 8th March 2023)

This was a short video that has now 6 visualisations on YouTube (2 in the last 6 months). No significant statistics in this case.

5.4.3.5 START Webinar #02 - 2023-04-26 (published on 2nd May 2023)

The visualisations at this point are 29 (+5). The average view duration is 43 s, and the average percentage viewed is 0.9%.

Figure 15 Statistics for visualisations of the START Webinar#02 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

Figure 16: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START Webinar#02 video on YouTube.

5.4.3.1 START Webinar #03, D. Crane presentation - 2023-05-31 (published on 12th July 2023)

This video is the second most viewed on the channel, the views being now 77 are (+18). The average view duration is 3m29 s, and the average percentage viewed is 7.4%.

Figure 17: Statistics for visualisations of the presentation by D. Crane in the START Webinar#03 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 18: Statistics for retention of viewers during the presentation by D. Crane in the START Webinar#03 video on YouTube.

5.4.3.2 START Webinar #03, J. Hollis presentation - 2023-05-31 (published on 14th July 2023)

This video collected 1 more view in the last semester, reaching 12. The average view duration is 36 s, and the average percentage viewed is 2.5%, so stats are not very significant.

5.4.3.3 START Webinar #03, START partners presentations - 2023-05-31 (published on 17th July 2023)

This video added 6 views in the last 6 months to reach 28. The average view duration is 2m 53 s, and the average percentage viewed is 6.3%.

Figure 19: Statistics for visualisations of the presentation by various START partners in the START Webinar#03 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 20: Statistics for retention of viewers during the presentation by various START partners in the START Webinar#03 video on YouTube.

5.4.3.4 START LCA Workshop - 2023-06-23 (published on 21st July 2023)

8 more visualisations came for this video, that is now at 29. The average view duration is 40 s, and the average percentage viewed is 1.5%.

Another video with the full footage has not been disclosed, because it contains the second part of the workshop that is confidential for the consortium partners.

Figure 21: Statistics for visualisations of the LCA Workshop on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 22: Statistics for retention of viewers of the LCA Workshop video on YouTube.

5.4.3.5 Starty #2 video (published on 18th October 2023)

There were 9 more views for this video (now 13). Statistics are not significant.

5.4.3.6 START Webinar #04 - 2024-03-14 (published on 15th March 2024)

This new video with the full footage of the Webinar #4 held in March collected 44 views in just about 40 days. As visible in Figure 23, this was automatically remarked by YouTube as above average for the channel. The average view duration is 7m 56 s, and the average percentage viewed is 8.5%.

Figure 23: Statistics for visualisations of the full footage of START Webinar#04 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 24: Statistics for retention of viewers during the full footage of START Webinar#04 video on YouTube.

5.4.3.7 *Starty volumes 1-3 (published on 21st March 2024)*

This video includes all the tables for the first 3 issues of Starty's comics. The views collected in just above 1 month on YT are 3, but it has been used in the PDAC exhibition without connection to YT (see the relevant chapter).

5.4.4 *Activity on Twitch*

Twitch has not been used yet.

5.4.5 *Activity on SlideShare*

As already reported in the previous deliverables D6.3, D6.4, and D6.6, SlideShare had been used to host documents prepared that were also uploaded to the website, and some on Zenodo. In the following Table 2 the views collected on SlideShare are shown for each item.

Table 2: Presentations and documents uploaded to Slideshare in previous periods and their performance. In parenthesis, the change from the previous deliverable D6.6, i.e., the status in November 2023).

PRESENTATION/ DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
"Green energy harvesting – State of the art"	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/green-energy-harvesting	44 views (+21)
"Project START: From WASTE to HIGH-TECH", presentation at EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention 2022 (Santiago de Chile, 3-4 November 2022) given by Daniel de Oliveira (LNEG).	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/project-start-from-waste-to-hightech	15 views (+3)
Presentation at World PM 2022 (Lyon, 9-13	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/presentations-at-world-pm2022	10 views (+2)

October 2022) given by Filipe Neves (LNEG).		
START Factsheet in Portuguese.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sistemas-sustentveis-de-captura-de-energia-baseados- numa-abordagem-inovadora-de-reciclagem-de-resduos-de-mina	5 views (+0)
START Factsheet in English.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sustainable-energy-harvesting-systems-based-on-innovative-mine-waste-recycling	5 views (+1)
START Flyer.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/start-flyer-254343547	6 views (+0)
START Newsletter Issue #1	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue1pdf	17 views (+8)
Stary Explains START – The comics (multilingual)	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startyexplainsstartpdf	5 views (+1)
START Newsletter Issue #2	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue2pdf	16 views (+16, uploaded 28/05/2023)

In the last period, only a few more documents were added to SlideShare (Table 3), for a total of 13.

Table 3: Presentations and documents uploaded to SlideShare in the last period and their performance.

PRESENTATION/ DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
Powder Metallurgy Review, Spring 2023	https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/powder-metallurgy-review-spring-2023-b6aa/263358173	2 views (uploaded on 13th November 2023)
START Newsletter Issue #3	https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/start-newsletter-3/264082754	9 views (uploaded 29/11/2023)
START Supercluster Event Abstract	https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/startsupercluster2023finalpdf	9 views (uploaded on 16/11/2023)
START Newsletter Issue #4	https://es.slideshare.net/slideshow/eu-start-project-start-newsletter-issue-4-pdf/268586918	37 views (uploaded 16/05/2024)

5.5 START NEWSLETTER

The project's Newsletter is published on its website and social media every 6 months, starting from Issue 1 at M06, November 2022. The name was decided among the consortium to be "RECOVER – REFORM - REUSE": this was made to give more appeal to the newsletter. The consortium chose a name that is suggesting that the content will not be just related to START but will be connected with the sustainability solutions imagined, the ideas of recovering (mine wastes, heat), of transformation (of wastes into raw materials for thermoelectric devices, of otherwise dispersed heat into electrical energy), and of reusing (materials and energy achieved to obtain better efficiency).

The information conveyed in the various issues of the newsletter will in fact always include general information about START, thermoelectric materials, energy harvesting from waste heat, and linked sustainability topics, including state-of-the-art documents and scientific reviews, updates on project activities, project events and other dissemination topics, with invitation to join events where START will be featured, the description of consortium partners (typically 2 per issue), and all information

on the various ways to keep informed about START (links to website, social media, link to the contact and subscription forms, etc.).

Being completely public, the information in the Newsletter must be duly checked in order to avoid IPR management issues. The direct distribution is partly based on a list of subscribers (and partly on social media and other partners networks). To create this list, the website tool for registration is used, and social media posts attract new subscribers to the website tool.

Here we update the distribution data for the first two issues, and give some info on issue #3, that was published just before this deliverable.

The KPI foreseen for the newsletter is the distribution to at least 500 recipients for each issue.

5.5.1 Newsletter issue #1

Issue #1 was published on 28th November 2022 (and covered in deliverable D6.3). It consists of 11 pages.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 448 times, again a strong increase from the figure of 193 (6th May 2023). It is likely that some more downloads will happen when subsequent issues are published.

On LinkedIn this issue obtained more than 400 impressions, with about 100 clicks and a high engagement rate. Twitter gave almost 900 impressions in the first year. On Zenodo⁶ it was uploaded on 29th November 2022 and was viewed 38 times and downloaded 35 times (data of 24th April 2024).

In D6.3 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients; with time, downloads are now close to 500 (counting also clicks on X and LinkedIn, the 500 has been passed), and still increasing.

5.5.2 Newsletter issue #2

The Issue 2 of the newsletter was first published on 22nd May 2023 (see D6.4) and had more than double pages compared to #1 (23 compared to 11).

In D6.4 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 332 times. Again, it is likely that some more downloads will happen when subsequent issues are published.

On LinkedIn this issue obtained about 250 impressions in the first months, and X reported about 460 impressions. On Zenodo⁷ it was uploaded on 25th May 2023 and was viewed 53 times and downloaded 33 times (data of 24th April 2024).

Thus, downloads are now about 360, plus some clicks on X and LinkedIn.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/7377126>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/7925963>

5.5.3 Newsletter issue #3

The Issue 3 of the newsletter was published on 29th November 2023 (see D6.6). It consists of 25 pages, 2 more than Issue #2.

In D6.6 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 197 times, and more downloads will happen later.

On LinkedIn this issue obtained about 250 impressions in the first months, and X reported about 460 impressions. On Zenodo⁸ and SlideShare⁹ it was uploaded on 29th November 2023 and was viewed 51 times and downloaded 14 times (data of 24th April 2024).

5.5.4 Newsletter issue #4

The Issue #4 of the newsletter was published on 30th April 2024. It consists of 27 pages, 2 more than Issue #3.

The newsletter was uploaded to the website on the Documents page (with reference also in the News page) on 7th May 2024 and was uploaded also to Zenodo¹⁰ and SlideShare¹¹ on 16th May. It was advertised on LinkedIn (7th May 2024) and X (9th May 2024). A mailing to the START mailing list was carried out on 14th May 2024. The launch of Issue #4 was also announced on the EPMA weekly Newsletter for members in the third week of May 2024 and later to non-members (about 1600 and 400 contacts, respectively). A news item on the EPMA quarterly newsletter will be sent to all EPMA members (about 1600 contacts) later in 2024. The data for downloads will be analysed in the next weeks.

5.6 START COMICS - STARTY

As already explained in previous Deliverables, START is making use of a comics character, “Starty, the robot”, that will be employed as much as possible to make communication more appealing also to those categories in the target that are not too scientifically involved in the subject, including the general public. This character will guide the reader or viewer into the START contents. Starty was already used as the main character in many videos and in the various issues of the Newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE”.

Starty strips were also translated in other languages: the first issue in 11 more languages, the 2nd in 12 languages, and the 3rd (and subsequent editions) in 14 languages. The translation effort includes not only the translation of the text, but also the adaptation of each comics balloon to each language, so each version needs to be graphically reworked. The list of languages is the following:

- Catalan
- Danish
- German

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/7925963>

⁹ <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/start-newsletter-3/264082754>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/10979280>

¹¹ https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/eu-start-project-start-newsletter_issue_4-pdf/268586918

- English
- Spanish
- French
- Italian
- Dutch
- Norwegian
- Polish
- Portuguese
- Slovak
- Turkish
- Japanese
- Hungarian

In Newsletter #1, Starty had 2 pages, in Newsletter Issue #2, #3 and #4 3 pages.

Starty will also be the main character of the “serious game”, that is under development within WP7 activities and will be reported in deliverable D7.2 - Serious Game.

5.7 VIDEOS

According to what was planned in the proposal, at least 5 videos will be produced during the project:

- 2 short videos (0.5-1 min), one at the start of the project to raise awareness and one at the end to summarise results. The language should be suitable for a wider audience; animations or cartoons could be used to attract non-specialists. One video at M04 (September 2022), one at M48 (May 2026).
- 2 longer videos (but still not too long, max 3 min) during the project, focusing on project topics and activities. The target should be more to groups 2-3, i.e., scientists, engineers, and entrepreneurs. Both videos are due at M48 (May 2026)
- 1 detailed video (about 5 min) at mid project (M24, May 2024), highlighting the results of the first part of the project (in fact, this will be postponed to November 2024).

Other videos could be produced, like:

- Interviews with key partners, describing the project or specific topics
- Recording of presentations given in events
- Short ads for specific events or for the “serious game”

EPMA normally is the partner taking care of producing the videos but will ask all relevant partners to help by delivering videos, images, and text. The videos are hosted on YouTube and/or Twitch, embedded in the START website, and posted on other social media like LinkedIn and Twitter/X.

The KPIs decided for these tools are the views achieved: minimum of 100 views per video is the base KPI, and an overall average above 200 views/video is an additional KPI. Social media analysis tools allow collecting further information about the audience (including additional views). We will apply these KPIs to the forecast videos mentioned above, and not to all additional videos.

5.7.1 *START introductory video*

A short introductory video for the project, created in September 2022, where Starty gives the introductory info about START. The video is present on YouTube, the website, LinkedIn and X, plus has been used in many dissemination events.

This is the situation of views on YouTube on 25th April 2024:

- YouTube (published on 25th October 2022):
 - views: 120
 - Average duration of viewing: 0m27s
 - Average view rate, %: 31.2%

As documented in the previous deliverable D6.4, LinkedIn¹² gave immediately about 800 additional views, while X contributed with 60 more impressions with the first post; about 30 more with subsequent posts (these numbers have not been further updated). Thus, the number of views, especially from LinkedIn, largely exceeds the minimum set, and is also way above the average requested of 200.

5.7.2 *Other videos uploaded in earlier periods*

5.7.2.1 Presentation of START at the Science Week 2022, Madrid

Video not produced by the project, but recorded by the event organisers, and made available (it is in Spanish): 201 views on YouTube now.

5.7.2.2 8th March videos

Self-recorded by the two female members of the START team on the International Women Day 2023. On the website's News page, 12 visualisations. On YouTube, a total of 13 views. On LinkedIn page, 148 and 151 video views. On Twitter, 96 impressions and 13 total engagements.

5.7.2.3 Webinar #01

Footage of the first START webinar, held on 28th February 2023 (1 h 3 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 52. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 174 (+115 on a private account) and 309 views, respectively.

5.7.2.4 Webinar #02

Footage of the second START webinar, held on 26th April 2023 (1 h 17 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 29. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 133 (+139 on a private account) and 558 views, respectively.

5.7.2.5 Webinar #03 - Crane

Footage of the first presentation in the third START webinar, held on 31st May 2023 (47 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 77. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 317 (+303 on a private account) and 81 views, respectively.

¹² LinkedIn data are available until 1 year after the publication, after that the posts and their related data are not retrievable anymore.

5.7.2.6 Webinar #03 - Hollis

Footage of the second presentation in the third START webinar, held on 31st May 2023 (24.5 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 12. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 363 (+149 on a private account) and 173 views, respectively.

5.7.2.7 Webinar #03 – Consortium partners

Footage of the other presentations in the third START webinar, held on 31st May 2023 (46 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 28. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 148 (+218 on a private account) and 1304 views, respectively.

5.7.2.8 LCA workshop

Footage of the START workshop webinar, held on 23rd June 2023 (45 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 29. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 235 (+307 on a private account) and 102 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.7.2.9 Starty #2

Video of the second Starty comics, published on 18th October 2023 (2 m 19 s). On YouTube, the number of views is 13. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 277 (+300 on a private account) and 447 views, respectively.

5.7.3 Other videos uploaded in the last 6 months

5.7.3.1 Webinar #4

Full footage of the fourth START webinar, held on 14th March 2024 (1 h 33 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 44. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 382 and 105 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.7.3.2 Starty volumes 1-3

This video includes all the tables for the first 3 issues of Starty's comics and was published on YouTube on 21st March 2024. The views collected YouTube are 3, but it has been used in the PDAC exhibition (see the relevant chapter).

5.8 CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

5.8.1 KPIs

KPIs are “a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective”. Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or a social media that is normal.

To assess the dissemination, START will collect metrics from the website, and the social media, and will compare some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet of the years. A list of the KPIs imagined, with their reference values, is given in Table 4. Note that the KPI for Twitter/X has been modified to be more realistic during the revision of the DCP, so that now a KPI on Impressions is envisaged (before the KPIs were on followers, and were deemed to be utterly unattainable, also because of the reduced interest for X in the targeted audience).

Table 4: KPIs considered for D&C activities (after DCP update at M24).

Tool	KPI	Reference value
Project website	Visitors	Year 1: 2000 Year 4: 4000
Twitter	Impressions	Year 4: 15000/yr
LinkedIn	Followers	End:800
Videos	Views	More than 100/video Average 200
Newsletters	Addressees	More than 500/issue
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Audience	100
Serious online game	Visitors	300
Other publications	Reach	More than 400000

According to previous project experiences, as already shown in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), an Excel file, named Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (MTOD) is used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest raised.

This is located on the START SharePoint (its address is [START/Work Packages/WP6 - Dissemination and communication/START Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination.xlsx¹³](#)) and contains all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A view of the present status of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 25.

The file allows to calculate total audience and views of the actions, and the ratio between views and audience for each action. In this way, during the project course, priorities about the social media could be given.

The data from MTOD is used to update the Funding & Tender website page on Dissemination (see 5.8.3). At present, about 390 lines are included in the file; the sum of all audience data is about 3.5M and the sum of views is more than 76k. Views have had highs of about 1850 (on Twitter) and 1400 (on LinkedIn), with a median of about 140 and an average of about 200 (slightly decreasing from the previous data).

We believe that the overall social media performance can be considered satisfactory: views have a remarkable median and average, so many of the followers actually visualise our content.

¹³ Note: this is a private address, not accessible from outside the Consortium.

The image shows a very dense table with approximately 390 rows and several columns. The table is mostly green, with some red highlights. The columns include activity names, dates, and status indicators. The table is oriented vertically on the page.

Figure 25: The Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (status on 10/05/2024, about 390 activities listed, one per line). In green, data that are considered final (in red, data that are not final but could be finalised as the date is after the expected end date).

5.8.1.1 LinkedIn

For LinkedIn, the number of followers is now above 515 (see also chapter 5.4.2), that is still below the target of 800 followers at the end of the project, but in line with the possibility of reaching the KPI at the end of the project. A plot of the number of new followers (see Figure 26) shows some correlation with the newsletters and the webinars, but also with the times when many invitations to follow the page have been sent (there is a 100 invitations per month limit). Page views, show more than 1000 visitors in 1 year (Figure 27). Impressions reached more than 15000 (Figure 28).

Figure 26: LinkedIn Follower metrics (last 365 days until 26 April 2024).

Figure 27: LinkedIn Page views metrics (last 365 days).

Figure 28: LinkedIn Impressions metrics (last 365 days).

5.8.1.2 Twitter – now X

For Twitter/X the number of actual followers (currently at 192) is considered to be underperforming. This can be explained by the relative lack of project news and activities, which are planned to expand from year 2 onwards, and also by the turmoil regarding Twitter itself as a platform (acquisition of Twitter – including the “political” debate about the new owner -, transformation into X, monetisation of the platform). This issue has been addressed by the KPI change from the number of followers to the yearly number of impressions, which is considered to be a better measurement target. The number of audiences reached – counting the number of views/impressions, Likes, Retweets, Engagements, Detail Expands, New followers and Profile visits – reached close to 5000 between 13 November 2023 and 2 May 2024: this number corresponds to real engagement with the project posts. The first two figures below (Figure 29, Figure 30) show the START X activity for the period covered by this Deliverable. Figure 31 shows Impressions collected over the Month of March for the 10 posts that were published.

Your posts earned **2.8K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Figure 29: Twitter impressions and Tweets from 01/12/23 to 29/02/2024

Tweet activity

Mar 1

Your posts earned **1.3K impressions** over this **63 day** period

Figure 30: Twitter impressions and Tweets from 01/03/24 to 02/05/2024.

Your posts earned **696 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Figure 31: Twitter impressions and Tweets in March 2024.

It must be noted that in addition to these posts, on X, LPRC has in many cases reposted news from other accounts, concerning raw materials, sustainability, thermoelectrics, waste heat recovery, etc. This helped in growing the follower base and kept the account busy between project posts. We have not counted these views and impressions, but they surely contribute to the visibility of the account.

5.8.1.3 Videos

The KPIs for video are: at least 100 views each, and an average of 200 views. As we are producing a large number of videos compared to the original number of 5, it would be really difficult to maintain this as a general rule. We will apply only to the 5 “institutional” videos. Only the first one has been prepared until now, the introductory video. It exceeds the KPI, considering all views on all platforms and not only on YouTube.

- Introductory video:
 - YouTube: 120 views
 - LinkedIn: about 800 in the first year
 - Twitter about 60 in the first year (so the total amount on social media is about 860 views).

So, the KPI of at least 100 views, and even the average expected of 200 views, are exceeded by far.

For the other videos, we have collected now more than 260 views on YouTube and many more on LinkedIn, both when the videos have been posted directly (e.g., about 300 for the International Women Day videos) and definitely much more as views of the posts.

For the webinar footage videos we felt that the length made them not so appealing, only a few viewers have watched the whole Webinar #1 and #2 events apart from those who were present live. For this reason, the third webinar had been split in three shorter videos, and this paid off especially for the video of the presentation of D. Crane that is the second most viewed.

For Webinar #4 we went back to the full footage video, and this achieved a good response for the moment (more than average in the first 40 days). We will consider both options for Webinar #5.

A second “institutional” video has been postponed (from M24 to M30) due to the workload and the possibility of including more results by making it a bit later.

5.8.1.4 Project website

Concerning the project website, we remind that the analysis is limited to the data after 17th October 2022 as because of an erroneous setting of Google Analytics all data before that date have been lost.

For all the available periods, these data have been collected:

- Audience (users, new users, numbers of sessions per user, pageviews, pages/session)
- Acquisition
- Behaviour (visited pages)

In the following pages we switch to the new data available for the website (from 5th July 2023 when the change in Google Analytics already mentioned in D6.6 took place).

A chart of the activity on pages in 2023 is shown in Figure 32. There are no evident activities linked to bots (and not to particular activities of advertisement by the consortium) so we conclude that all data are linked to “normal” traffic.

Views by Page path and screen class over time

Figure 32: Page Views in the last 6 months for the project website. No particular activities seem due to “bots”.

Figure 33 shows the Audience data for this last period, including Views and Users.

The most visited page is still the home page, and 7 main pages are in the most visited 8 pages. The only news items that are in the first 10 are those on the 4th webinar registration and the footage, and the Newsletter Issue #3. The total views of about 2700 would scale on a yearly basis to about 6000, that is, already above the KPI of 4000/yr that is due at the end of the project and growing from the previous period (it was around 5000, and 3600 in the first year).

Per user, the most viewed page is still the News page.

Users were about 1700 (3700/yr) compared to below 1200 for the previous period, thus growing as well.

Sessions are estimated to be about 3350/yr (1500 in this period).

Views-Users				
Period:	14/11/2023	25/04/2024	Days:	164
Page	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time
Total/365 days	5966.9	3705.6		
Total/average	2681	1665	1.61	23.33
/	1287	848	1.52	19.95
/documents/	352	181	1.94	25.94
/the-project/	250	153	1.63	20.24
/news/	172	72	2.39	34.15
/consortium/	125	73	1.71	35.47
/multimedia/	113	60	1.88	32.15
/register-for-our-4th-webinar-on-march-14th/	86	53	1.62	29.13
/contact/	75	60	1.25	11.13
/download-recover-reform-reuse-issue-3-nov-2023/	63	50	1.26	16.48
/watch-the-footage-from-our-4th-webinar-on-powder-metallurgy-in-start/	40	22	1.82	17.86
/start-featured-on-the-innovation-news-network-website/	27	17	1.59	22.88
/start-will-speak-in-the-incomess-final-workshop/	15	8	1.88	26.88
/starty-is-back-in-13-languages/	15	12	1.25	22.75
/starts-1st-annual-meeting-successfully-run-in-madrid/	12	10	1.20	55.60
/start-webinar-3-start-partners-share-knowledge-about-tetrahydrites-in-europe/	8	7	1.14	23.71
/watch-the-lecture-by-3drivers-on-use-of-lca-for-environmental-impact-assessment/	7	6	1.17	4.00
/join-the-third-webinar-on-may-31st-live-from-our-project-meeting/	4	4	1.00	58.50
/start-on-powder-metallurgy-review/	4	4	1.00	16.50
/start-webinar-3-watch-doug-cranes-speech-on-thermoelectric-energy-harvesting/	4	4	1.00	33.50
/start-webinar-3-watch-julie-hollis-speech-on-the-eus-crm-ambitions-ant-the-role-of-eurogeosurveys/	4	4	1.00	11.75
/starty-comics-starty-explains-start-now-available-in-12-languages/	3	3	1.00	22.00
/*	2	2	1.00	17.50
/start-looks-southwest-the-second-start-webinar-connects-to-latin-america/	2	1	2.00	307.00
/the-project-scientific-advisory-board-has-been-appointed/	2	2	1.00	14.00
/[Anhang	1	1	1.00	0.00
/author/rrayez/	1	1	1.00	0.00
/iwd2023/	1	1	1.00	9.00
/more-than-60-participants-in-starts-first-free-webinar/	1	1	1.00	33.00
/news-start-wpm2022/	1	1	1.00	8.00
/news-we-started/	1	1	1.00	26.00
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-1-our-start-newsletter-is-here/	1	1	1.00	19.00
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-2-is-now-available-may-2023/	1	1	1.00	57.00
/the-footage-of-the-second-start-free-webinar-dedicated-to-latin-america-is-now-available/	1	1	1.00	18.00

Figure 33: Views and Users data per page for the project website (14/11/2023 to 25/04/2024) and projections to 1 yr data.

Landing page	14/11/2023	25/04/2024	Days:	164
Landing page	Sessions	Users	New users	Average engagement time per session
Total/365 days	3345.1	2655.2	2299.1	
Total/average	1503	1193	1033	25.17
/	1038	827	805	27.04
/documents	119	87	62	24.65
(not set)	87	66	0	2.20
/register-for-our-4th-webinar-on-march-14th	44	42	38	28.23
/download-recover-reform-reuse-issue-3-nov-2	42	39	37	15.50
/watch-the-footage-from-our-4th-webinar-on-t	28	20	15	23.36
/multimedia	23	11	6	20.70
/the-project	22	19	10	55.59
/contact	20	20	16	5.45
/consortium	18	8	5	25.94
/start-featured-on-the-innovation-news-netwo	14	13	11	16.50
/news	10	6	2	8.50
/start-will-speak-in-the-incomess-final-workshc	7	7	3	26.71
/starts-1st-annual-meeting-successfully-run-in-	7	7	6	33.14
/start-on-powder-metallurgy-review	4	4	4	105.25
/watch-the-lecture-by-3drivers-on-use-of-lca-fc	4	3	2	1.25
/join-the-third-webinar-on-may-31st-live-from-	3	3	2	107.67
/starty-is-back-in-13-languages	3	2	1	16.33
	2	1	0	36.50
/*	2	2	2	17.50
/[Anhang	1	1	1	0.00
/author/rrayez	1	1	1	0.00
/news-start-wpm2022	1	1	1	8.00
/start-webinar-3-watch-doug-cranes-speech-or	1	1	1	93.00
/start-webinar-3-watch-julie-hollis-speech-on-t	1	1	1	23.00
/starty-comics-starty-explains-start-now-availa	1	1	1	53.00

Figure 34: Sessions and Users data per page for the project website (14/11/2023 to 25/04/2024) and projections to 1 yr data.

The distribution by countries (Figure 35) shows an increasing engagement led by USA and Portugal. Most of the main countries have increased and even more than doubled the users. Visibility is clearly extended to the whole world.

Looking at the sources for connections to the website (Figure 36), most happen directly via typing in the address bar in the browser (probably using Favourites bookmarks), followed by Google searches. LinkedIn is the 3rd contributor, then Sendinblue (now Brevo, the provider of our mailing service, so clicks on the mails that we deliver to our mailing list). Baidu (Chinese search engine) and Twitter (t.co) are also at the top of the list. Some other referrals are via project partners' websites (EPMA, LNEG, GeniCore, 3drivers, LPRC), and to events where START is included in the useful links (for instance the InComEss Final Workshop). The Innovation News Network banner also led to some traffic.

Concerning connection devices, the ratio between desktop and mobile devices stays above 3, and also desktop users seem to have higher engagement (Figure 37).

Country	14/11/2023	25/04/2024			Days:	164
Country	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time
United States	152	151	21	0.13	0.14	12.72
Portugal	120	112	149	0.61	1.24	70.33
Netherlands	112	111	74	0.50	0.66	32.23
Germany	58	55	37	0.49	0.64	51.43
France	57	56	47	0.44	0.82	36.11
Finland	55	55	13	0.21	0.24	11.95
Spain	55	45	51	0.64	0.93	55.35
Austria	50	50	14	0.28	0.28	9.74
United Kingdom	44	41	36	0.54	0.82	62.70
India	39	39	20	0.45	0.51	21.72
Poland	32	30	39	0.54	1.22	49.38
Norway	27	27	10	0.29	0.37	48.63
China	24	21	1	0.04	0.04	7.83
Italy	23	21	30	0.49	1.30	54.43
Ireland	18	18	1	0.05	0.06	0.78
Japan	16	16	12	0.71	0.75	34.00
Belgium	15	14	10	0.53	0.67	16.93
Denmark	13	12	6	0.40	0.46	16.46
Sri Lanka	13	13	4	0.31	0.31	9.92
Sweden	11	11	4	0.36	0.36	5.55
Vietnam	9	9	1	0.10	0.11	3.00
Brazil	8	7	6	0.67	0.75	20.00
Uganda	8	8	5	0.45	0.63	49.00
Russia	6	6	3	0.43	0.50	96.83
Türkiye	6	6	2	0.20	0.33	3.83
Pakistan	5	5	2	0.33	0.40	17.40
Romania	5	5	3	0.50	0.60	14.00
Singapore	5	5	2	0.29	0.40	9.20
Indonesia	4	4	1	0.25	0.25	1.25
Mexico	4	4	3	0.75	0.75	60.00
South Korea	4	4	3	0.60	0.75	179.75
Switzerland	4	4	3	0.75	0.75	109.50
Canada	3	3	0	0.00	0.00	0.33
Greece	3	3	1	0.33	0.33	10.00
Kazakhstan	3	3	3	0.75	1.00	67.67
Slovakia	3	3	4	0.50	1.33	151.67
Thailand	3	3	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Armenia	2	2	0	0.00	0.00	1.50
Colombia	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	25.00
Czechia	2	2	2	1.00	1.00	46.50
Georgia	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	6.50
Ghana	2	2	2	1.00	1.00	7.50
Hungary	2	2	2	0.40	1.00	340.00
Iran	2	1	2	1.00	1.00	104.50
Latvia	2	2	4	0.50	2.00	30.50
Malta	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	7.00
Nicaragua	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	13.50
Nigeria	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	171.50
Peru	2	2	0	0.00	0.00	3.50
Philippines	2	2	2	1.00	1.00	3.50
Serbia	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	6.00
United Arab Emirates	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	52.50
Argentina	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	4.00
Australia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	20.00
Bulgaria	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	5.00
Cuba	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cyprus	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	9.00
Dominican Republic	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	14.00
Ecuador	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Egypt	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Estonia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	8.00
Ethiopia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	106.00
French Guiana	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	5.00
Iraq	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	17.00
Jordan	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	2.00
Lithuania	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	9.00
Malaysia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Morocco	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	50.00
Paraguay	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	1.00
Saudi Arabia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	25.00
Slovenia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	1.00
Somalia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	12.00
Taiwan	1	1	2	1.00	2.00	22.00
Ukraine	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	15.00
Uzbekistan	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	14.00
Venezuela	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	5.00

Figure 35: Users and Sessions by Country data for the project website (14/11/2023 to 25/04/2024).

Sources		14/11/2023	25/04/2024			Days:	164
Period:							
Session source/medium	Users	Sessions	Engaged sessions	Average engagement time per session	Engaged sessions per user	Events per session	Engagement rate
(direct) / (none)	538	664	250	20.76	0.46	4.33	0.38
google / organic	283	385	185	30.56	0.65	5.15	0.48
linkedin.com / referral	60	136	81	29.93	1.35	5.11	0.60
6fgo6.r.a.d.sendibm1.com / referral	38	41	6	7.98	0.16	3.34	0.15
6fgo6.r.ag.d.sendibm3.com / referral	32	37	11	10.43	0.34	3.27	0.30
6fgo6.r.sp1-brevo.net / referral	16	16	2	2.94	0.13	3.44	0.13
baidu / organic	15	15	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00
9uxmp.r.a.d.sendibm1.com / referral	14	21	9	19.71	0.64	4.52	0.43
t.co / referral	13	22	13	18.00	1.00	5.55	0.59
(not set)	10	10	0	24.40	0.00	3.20	0.00
epma.com / referral	10	11	6	64.27	0.60	6.73	0.55
lneg.pt / referral	10	25	8	34.08	0.80	4.64	0.32
bing / organic	8	12	8	75.00	1.00	9.33	0.67
genicore.eu / referral	5	6	6	128.00	1.20	12.17	1.00
innovationnewsnetwork.com / referral	5	33	26	39.15	5.20	7.12	0.79
m.facebook.com / referral	4	4	1	0.00	0.25	3.50	0.25
reesilience.eu / referral	4	4	2	24.75	0.50	4.75	0.50
3drivers.pt / referral	3	6	4	5.83	1.33	3.33	0.67
lnkd.in / referral	3	4	3	11.25	1.00	4.00	0.75
eis-he.eu / referral	2	15	10	37.47	5.00	7.07	0.67
incomess-project.com / referral	2	7	5	21.86	2.50	5.29	0.71
l.facebook.com / referral	2	2	2	39.50	1.00	7.50	1.00
6fgo6.r.bh.d.sendibt3.com / referral	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00
cienciavitae.pt / referral	1	1	1	26.00	1.00	7.00	1.00
duckduckgo / organic	1	2	1	13.00	1.00	5.50	0.50
e.mail.ru / referral	1	2	1	17.00	1.00	3.50	0.50
edgeservices.bing.com / referral	1	7	5	14.57	5.00	5.29	0.71
epslarhome.shop / referral	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00
l.instagram.com / referral	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00
lapalmacentre.eu / referral	1	2	0	0.00	0.00	2.50	0.00
lm.facebook.com / referral	1	1	1	5.00	1.00	4.00	1.00
macaronight.eu / referral	1	4	3	72.75	3.00	10.50	0.75
pradoposgrado2324.ugr.es / referral	1	1	1	180.00	1.00	8.00	1.00
repositorio.lneg.pt / referral	1	2	2	111.00	2.00	7.50	1.00
statics.teams.cdn.office.net / referral	1	2	0	0.00	0.00	2.50	0.00
testepma.com / referral	1	1	0	2.00	0.00	4.00	0.00
webgate.acceptance.ec.europa.eu / referral	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00
yahoo / organic	1	1	1	10.00	1.00	4.00	1.00

Figure 36: Users and Sessions by Sources and referrals data for the project website (14/11/2023 to 25/04/2024).

Devices		14/11/2023	25/04/2024			Days:	164
Period:							
Device category	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagem ent rate	Engaged sessions per use	Average engagement time	
desktop	811	784	550	0.45	0.68	40.55	
mobile	246	246	102	0.37	0.41	20.02	
tablet	3	3	2	0.67	0.67	7.33	

Figure 37: Users and Sessions by Devices data for the project website (14/11/2023 to 25/04/2024).

Globally, we can consider the website performance even more satisfactory than in previous periods, that is also understandable as the project is running well and begins to deliver its important results. We clearly hope the performance will improve even more.

5.8.1.5 *Newsletter*

Concerning the newsletter, the distribution through the START mailing list now comprises just above 200 names. As mentioned elsewhere, EPMA sends the link to download the various Newsletter issues to about 1600 EPMA member contacts via its weekly E-Mail Newsletter and in subsequent Newsletters to non-member contacts (about 400).

Thus, especially via the EPMA distribution, the target of 500 has been exceeded by far for all issues of the newsletter; clearly it must be correlated with the actual downloads recorded, but data for Issue #1 are also growing to above the 500 mark and this could happen with time for all subsequent issues.

5.8.2 *WP6 meetings*

During this semester, only smaller meetings were organised for specific discussions, in particular for clustering reasons:

- 7 December 2023 WP6 Deliverables (EPMA-LNEG) (online)
- 11 December 2023 WP6 Potential synergies START-THERMOS (LNEG, EPMA, THERMOS partners)
- 11 January 2024 WP6 START INN article (LNEG, EPMA)
- 25 January 2024 WP6 START Training organisation (ASGMI, LNEG, EPMA)
- 8 February 2024 WP6 START INN article (LNEG, EPMA)
- 13 March 2024 WP6 START Webinar #4 last details (LNEG, EPMA)
- 8 April 2024 WP6 START-THERMOS meeting preparation (LNEG, EPMA, SINTEF)
- 11 April 2024 WP6 START-THERMOS meeting (LNEG, EPMA, SINTEF, TEGnology, RGS, MBN, THERMOS partners)
- 17 April 2024 WP6 START-Webinar #5 Technical test (EPMA, SINTEF)
- 22 April 2024 WP6 START-Webinar #5 Technical test (EPMA, SINTEF)
- 22 April 2024 WP6 START-THERMOS Industrial Workshop organisation (LNEG, EPMA, SINTEF, TEGnology, RGS, MBN, LPRC, THERMOS partners)

The rest of the arrangement were discussed via E-Mail, bi- or multilaterally.

5.8.3 *Continuous reporting on Funding&Tender website*

The WP Leader (EPMA) is responsible of regularly updating the information on Dissemination and Communication in the relevant section in the project's Continuous Reporting on the Funding&Tender website. There are three pages dedicated to these topics on the portal: "Publications", "Dissemination" and "Communication".

At the latest, an update must be made before the end of each reporting period, as at each periodic report, all the information present in the Continuous Reporting section is automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report. This was done in August 2023 (M15), and for the moment the only changes have been made, either automatically or manually, on the Publications page. This page (Figure 38) contains many publications. The “Communication” (Figure 39) and the “Dissemination” pages (Figure 40) are not updated.

n002n7x4 (EXTERNAL)

Grant Management
Project Continuous Report

101058632 (START) HORIZON-IA

Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07

Project Summary

Researchers involved in the project

Deliverables

Milestones

Critical Risks

Publications

Results

Disseminati... activities

Communic... Activities

Standards

Intellectual property rights (IPR)

Datasets

Impact

Impact Continuation

Other Results

Publications SAVE

Project publications (19 publications)

[Export to Excel](#) [Add Publication](#)

	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	Peer-reviewed	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	PID (publisher version of record)	PID of deposited publication	Actions
1	Article in journal	The START project: Creatin	Filipe Neves; Bruno Vicenzi;	Powder Metallurgy Review n		False	True	10.5281/zenodo.7850149		
2	Publication in conference pi	REUSING SECONDARY MINEI	Neves, Filipe; de Oliveira, L	ZENODO		False	True	10.5281/zenodo.10213433		
3	Publication in conference pi	Presentation of the START	de Oliveira, Daniel	ZENODO		False	True	10.5281/zenodo.7327406	10.5281/zenodo.7327407	
4	Publication in conference pi	Presentation of the START	Neves, F.	ZENODO		False	True			
5	Books/monographs	Starty explains START	START Project			False	True	10.5281/zenodo.7746440	10.5281/zenodo.7746441	
6	Other	COMO GENERAR ELECTRICII	Ester Boixereu Vila; Concep			False	True	10.5281/zenodo.7417730		
7	Other	D6.1 - Creation of the proj	START project			False	True	10.5281/zenodo.8270292		
8	Other	D6.2 - Dissemination and C				False	False	10.5281/zenodo.10419388		
9	Other	D6.3 - Dissemination, outre				False	False	10.5281/zenodo.10419425		
10	Other	D6.4 - Dissemination, outre				False	False	10.5281/zenodo.10419481		

* "open access" means the practice of providing online access to research outputs resulting from actions funded under the Programme, in particular scientific publications and research data, free of charge to the end-user

Figure 38: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Publications on the Funding&Tender portal (25/04/2024).

n002n7x4 (EXTERNAL)
Grant Management
Project Continuous Report
HOW TO

101058632 (START) Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01 Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07	HORIZON-IA 	Project Summary 	Researchers involved in the project 	Deliverables 	Milestones 	Critical Risks 	Publications 	Results 	Disseminati... activities 	Communic... Activities 	Standards 	Intellectual property rights (IPR) 	Datasets 	Impact 	Impact Continuation 	Other Results
---	----------------	---------------------	---	------------------	----------------	--------------------	------------------	-------------	-------------------------------	----------------------------	---------------	--	--------------	------------	-------------------------	-------------------

Communications Activities

SAVE

Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome	Status	Actions
Technical promotional material	Leaflets, posters and roller banners to	Industry, business partn	Exhibition	No specific KPI for this activity	Ongoing	✗
Communication by social media	All project details (approach, activities	Citizens	Social media	Posts online: audience >500k cor	Ongoing	✗
RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue 2	Project newsletter. Information about j	Citizens	Newsletter	Delivered to 1600 + 400 EPMA cc	Delivered	✗
Starty the Robot	Cartoon character developed by the co	Citizens	Newsletter	Posts with Starty in 12 language:	Ongoing	✗
Communication by project website	All project details (approach, activities	Citizens	Website	>8000 page views until now (tar	Ongoing	✗
RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue 1	Project newsletter. Information about j	Citizens	Newsletter	Delivered to 1600 + 400 EPMA cc	Delivered	✗

Validate

Figure 39: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Communications on the Funding&Tender portal (25/04/2024).

n002n7x4 (EXTERNAL)

Grant Management
Project Continuous Report
 HOW TO

101058632 (START)	HORIZON-IA	Project Summary	Researchers involved in the project	Deliverables	Milestones	Critical Risks	Publications	Results	Disseminati... activities	Communic... Activities	Standards	Intellectual property rights (IPR)	Datasets	Impact	Impact Continuation	Other Results
Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01 Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07		✔	⚠	i	i	✔	i	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔

Dissemination Activities SAVE

There is no dissemination activity for this project yet

▼ List the dissemination activities carried out in the context of the project.
Include dissemination activities mentioned in the proposal and new ones.

[+ Add Dissemination Activity](#)

Dissemination Activity Name	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience Reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
EPMA Summer School START dissemination	Education and training events	Research communities, Industry, business partners	START lessons and experiences are given to participi	Ongoing	✘
Dissemination in scientific events	Conferences	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators	START is taking part in many scientific events to di	Ongoing	✘
Clustering	Clustering activities	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Meetings are being carried out with many of the pi	Ongoing	✘
Dissemination in Newsletter	Other	Other	In the Newsletter, START includes Technical Pills wit	Ongoing	✘
START webinars	Education and training events	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators	START organizes free webinars (3 to date) with pre	Ongoing	✘

Validate

Figure 40: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Dissemination on the Funding&Tender portal (25/04/2024).

6 TASK 6.2: TECHNICAL AND SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

All partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

- Relevant EPMA events (for the PM community mainly):
 - The EuroPM and/or WorldPM Congress and Exhibition series (a project booth is foreseen)
 - The EPMA technical seminars by sectors (Functional Materials, Hot Isostatic Pressing, etc.)
 - Sectoral Group meetings, e.g.:
 - European Functional Materials Sectoral Group (EuroFM)
 - European Hot Isostatic Pressing Sectoral Group (EuroHIP)
 - Environment, Health, Quality and Safety Working Group (EHQS).
- International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT/ACT conference series), and other conferences to be defined by the consortium.
- Special dissemination seminars and presentations (webinars or in person) on specific project-related topics:
 - contributions from the consortium
 - selected external speakers
 - ads on dedicated printed or online magazines (e.g., Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management, Journal of Environmental Management, Environmental Earth Sciences, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Mine Water and the Environment...)

External events to communicate to the public and to other scientific and industrial communities and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public: EPMA and other consortium partners will take part in

- At least 2 external events and exhibitions per year
- Possibly Science Festivals and Fairs (e.g., the European Researchers' Night) to communicate the scope of the project and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public.

Specific KPIs will be introduced to quantify the impact of project dissemination.

Publications and presentations in conferences, seminars and congresses are strongly encouraged: all consortium partners should try to organise a technical participation in an event to disseminate a part of the work carried out in START. This will broaden the audience for the project topics and in the end will create the condition for successful exploitation.

Thus, maybe with some exceptions, we expect that during the course of the project almost all partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

Addressing communities that are outside those already covered by the consortium members activities and by the standard journals, magazines and conferences/events is also rather important

for an innovative project like START. For this reason, the plan is to try addressing external communities by publishing well balanced papers and articles in more general magazines, or news services/websites (the Horizon Results, the Horizon Magazine, also suitable generic magazines, like for instance the Open Access Government magazine).

6.1 EVENTS LIST

In order to select the events where the partners, individually or as consortium, should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a “**START Events List**” is established and regularly updated by the WP6 leader (EPMA) on the START SharePoint and every partner will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what is the priority to give to this event in order to try maximising the impact by optimising the effort.
- Date of start of event
- Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)
- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition) etc.
- START Booth: whether a START booth should be present at the event
- Partner Booth: whether a START partner booth should be present at the event (including name of partner)
- START lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- START lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The list is the basis for discussion, in the meetings, about participation at the various events.

In Figure 41 the present status of the list is shown.

Event	Priority (1=high)	Date start	Date end	Physical /Online/ Hybrid	Website	Location	Type of audience	START Booth	Partner Booth	START lectures/papers	START lecture/paper date	Presenter	Reference partner	Attendees
ASGMI Mining Environmental Liabilities Workshop, Brazil	1.00	27/11/2023		Physical		Criciuma (Brasil)	Raw materials/mining	No					ASGMI	
GENERA 2024 (international Energy and Environment Fair)	3	06/02/2024	08/02/2024	Physical	https://www.ifema.es/en/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
PDAC 2024: The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention	1.00	03/03/2024	06/03/2024	Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/convention	Toronto (Canada)	Raw materials/mining						LNEG	
4th START Webinar	1	14/03/2024	14/03/2024	Online						Powder metallurgy technologies			LNEG	
TMS 2024 Annual Meeting & Exhibition	1.00	03/03/2024	07/03/2024	Physical	https://www.tms.org/TMS2024	Orlando (USA)	Materials	?		Technical presentation		P. Carvalho	SINTEF	
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	Apr-May 24		Physical	https://www.egu.eu/	Vienna (Austria)	Raw materials/mining							
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	Apr-May 24		Physical	https://www.eitmsummit.com/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining							
2024 MRS Spring Meeting & Exhibit	1.00	22/04/2024	26/04/2024	Physical	https://www.mrs.org/meetings-events/spr	Seattle WA (USA)	Materials	No		Technical presentation		A. Ray	RGS	
Hannover Messe 2024 (ENERGIZING A SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRY)	3.00	22/04/2024	26/04/2024	Physical	https://www.hannovermesse.de/en/	Hannover (Germany)								
Conference on Industrial Technologies IndTech 2024	n.d.	03/06/2024	05/06/2024	Physical	https://indtech2024.eu/	Namur (Belgium)								
5th START Webinar	1	07/06/2024	07/06/2024	Hybrid		Oslo (Norway)				TE devices			LNEG	
40th International & 20th European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT) 2024	1.00	30/06/2024	04/07/2024	Physical	https://ict2024.agh.edu.pl/en	Krakow (Poland)	Thermoelectric Academic					Maarten Den Heijer	RGS	
EPMA Summer School 2024	1	17/07/2024	21/07/2024	Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	Alessandria (Italy)	PM community	-	-	Thermoelectricity experience?		H. Yin?	EPMA	
Sustainable Minerals '24	n.d.	2024, Jul?		Physical	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-minerals-22/									
Researchers' Night 2024	1	27/09/2024	27/09/2024	Hybrid	https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/	Many	Academic, wide	-	-	?		?		
BSc/MSc free online training seminar/workshop	1	Sep 2024		Online	START website	-		-	-	Technical pres		Many		
EuroPM24	1	29/09/2024	02/10/2024	Physical	europm24.com	Malmö (Sweden)	PM community	Yes	-	Technical pres		Many	EPMA	
MMH (Mining and Minerals Hall)	n.d.	2024, Oct?			https://mmhseville.com/?lang=en	Sevilla	Mining							
CONAMA (biannual congress)	n.d.	2024, Oct?			http://www.fundacionconama.org/	Madrid	Sustainability					Ester Boixereu	IGME	
6th START Webinar (LNEG)	1	2024, Nov?		Online									LNEG	
Raw Materials Week 2024 (every year)	1	09/12/2024	13/12/2024	Physical									LNEG	
GENERA 2025 (international Energy and Environment Fair)	n.d.	2025, Feb?			https://www.ifema.es/en/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
7th START Webinar (LNEG)	n.d.	2025, Feb?		Online									LNEG	
EPMA FM or HIP seminar 2025	n.d.	2025, TBD		Hybrid	seminars.epma.com	TBD	PM community	-	-	Technical pres		?	EPMA	
TMS 2025 Annual Meeting & Exhibition	1.00	23/03/2024	27/03/2024	Physical	https://www.tms.org/AnnualMeeting/TMS2025	Las Vegas (USA)	Materials	?						
8th START Webinar (LNEG)	n.d.	25, May/June?		Hybrid									LNEG	
International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT) 2025	n.d.	2025, Jun/Jul		Physical		Sendai (Japan)	Thermoelectric Academic			to be considered for the following years		?		
EPMA Summer School 2025	n.d.	2025, Jun/Jul		Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	TBD	PM community	-	-	Demo START material?		?	EPMA	
Sustainable Minerals '25	n.d.	2025, Jul?		Physical	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-minerals-22/									

Figure 41: Status of the START Events List Excel file (updated 29/04/2024), section concerning the period between November 2023 and June 2025. In light green the events already covered.

The tool is updated about upcoming events, reassessing the priorities continuously. In general, some high priority recurring events are these:

- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) and International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT) conference series
- GENERA (International Energy and Environment Fair)
- Raw Materials Week
- EIT Raw Materials summit
- EU Sustainable Energy Week
- EU Green week
- EPMA's EuroPM Powder Metallurgy yearly Congress & Exhibition (was World PM in 2022)
- EPMA's seminars (HIP, Functional Materials)
- Sustainable Minerals
- In general, when partners have large internal events, these will be covered.

6.2 EVENTS COVERED IN M19-M24

The consortium continued to take part in events organised by third parties. Due to the winter period, there is as usual a slightly lower event activity, but in these months, we took part in some events anyway.

The partners most involved in the industrial side (and the consortium agreed) preferred to postpone participation in industrial events like trade fairs, more related to the application, to later years in the project, when more practical achievements could be shown to attract interest.

The consortium also organised a free webinar with good attendance.

Most of these activities can still be considered a mix of communication and dissemination.

6.2.1 Environmental liabilities workshop in Criciúma (Santa Catarina, Brazil)

A passive liabilities workshop was organised by ASGMI in Criciúma (Brazil) on 28th November - 1st December 2023. During the three days of the workshop, conferences¹⁴ about different topics related to mining environmental liabilities and their remediation in Ibero-America were held. In addition, a one-day field trip was organised in which a mine was visited, as well as different points around the city of Criciúma where the effects of environmental liabilities could be seen, and in some cases also liabilities that had been remediated using different methods.

Among the treated topics:

- management of environmental liabilities in different Ibero-American countries
- extraction of mineral resources from tailings
- use of those tailings to make construction materials
- geochemical and mineralogical characterization of tailings

¹⁴ <https://asgmi.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/00-Agenda-Taller-Pasivos-Ambientales-Mineros.pdf> (in Spanish)

- proposals for risks evaluation methodologies.

Dr. Fredy Guzmán (Mexican Geological Survey) and Dr. Cátia Prazeres (Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia) spoke about the START project and the contributions of the Mining Environmental Liabilities Expert Group of ASGMI to the Work Package 2 during their presentations.

Figure 42: Attendees at the Mining Environmental Liabilities workshop held in Criciúma, Santa Catarina, (Brazil).

6.2.2 *“Latin America – Europe: Cooperation opportunities for a more sustainable raw materials industry. The EU-AISiCal project case” workshop in Brasilia (Brazil)*

A workshop titled "Latin America – Europe: Cooperation Opportunities for a More Sustainable Raw Materials Industry: The EU-AISiCal Project Case" was held in Brasilia (Brazil) on 30th January - 1st February 2024. Organized by the ASGMI, to promote the AISiCal project in which ASGMI participates, the event aimed to foster dialogue on the challenges faced by the aluminium and metallurgical industries across their entire value chain, from resource extraction to finished product creation. This dialogue, involving industry, research, governance, and communities, specifically addressed the need to meet the rising demand for aluminium in the context of the energy transition, while ensuring sustainability, industry competitiveness and profitability, and social acceptance.

The workshop featured numerous presentations on topics including the state of raw materials in Ibero-America and Europe, advancements in raw material processing within the industry, and the role of modelling tools in innovation. Among these presentations, Dr Fredy Guzmán of the Mexican

Geological Survey (SGM) provided a talk highlighting the START project and its innovative contributions.

Figure 43: In this image, Dr. Fredy Guzmán, who serves as both the Head of Environmental Projects at the Mexican Geological Survey (SGM) and the Chair of the Mine Environmental Liabilities Group of ASGMI, is delivering his presentation titled "Identification, Characterization, and Recovery of Mining Environmental Liabilities" during the EU-AISiCal workshop held in Brasilia (Brazil).

Figure 44: Attendees at the EU-AISiCal workshop in Brasilia (Brazil).

6.2.3 *START at the ERHASE session in the InComEss Final Workshop, 31st January 2024*

InComEss

START was invited to join a special ERHASE session in the InComEss Final Workshop, where START, and also FAST-SMART and SYMPHONY, other partners in the ERHASE Cluster, presented their state-of-the-art. As this is an event related to clustering, details are given in the relevant chapter.

6.2.4 *START at the Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada (PDAC) Convention in Toronto, Canada, 3rd - 6th March 2024*

The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention¹⁵ is the event of choice for the world's mineral industry and this year it had almost 27000 participants. Led by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), and under the motto "European Union for a sustainable future" (Figure 45), the European Union (EU) booth accommodated and promoted EU research and innovation projects under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes, among many other activities. START was one of the 13 projects (the others being Semacret, Multiminer, Nexgen-Sims, Rotate, Digiecoquarry, m4mining, EIS, GREENPEG, S34I, MineI0, Vector, and Hephaestus) selected to join the EU booth at PDAC 2024 (Figure 46). Filipe Neves (LNEG) was the representative of the START project and during the first day of the convention it was possible to briefly present the project to Ms Marina Zanchi, Director of the HaDEA and Ms Katleen Engelbosch, Head of Department (Digital, Industry, and Space) at HaDEA (Figure 47). For the START project, the 4 days of PDAC2024 resulted in an excellent opportunity for networking and promoting START activities within the mineral exploration and mining community.

¹⁵ <https://www.pdac.ca/convention>

Figure 45: EU booth at PDAC 2024.

Figure 46: Projection of the START video in the Horizon Europe area of the EU booth.

Figure 47: (Left) Filipe Neves (START project coordinator) with Ms. Marina Zanchi, Director of HaDEA (on the right), and Ms. Katleen Engelbosch, Head of Department (Digital, Industry and Space) at HaDEA (center). (Right) Group photo of representatives of the H2020 and HE projects with Ms. Marina Zanchi, Director of HaDEA, and Ms. Katleen Engelbosch, Head of Department (Digital, Industry and Space) of HaDEA.

6.2.5 START Webinar #04 - 14th March 2024

Another free webinar, the fourth of the START series, has been organised for the 14th of March, 15:00-16:50 CET. It was titled “Powder technology for tetrahedrite p-type semiconductors”, and the speakers were three of our START consortium members. They reported on what is being done to transform the tetrahedrite mineral into a suitable thermoelectric material, using powder metallurgy. This was the programme of the event:

14:45 - Participants admission

15:00 - Bruno Vicenzi (European Powder Metallurgy Association) and Filipe Neves (LNEG) – Welcome and introduction

15:05 - Serena Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia Spa) – “Mechano-chemical synthesis of thermoelectrically-optimized tetrahedrites from mine tailing” + Q&A

15:40 - Damian Karpowicz (GeniCore Sp. Z. o.o.) – “U-FAST – devices for SPS technology” + Q&A

16:15 - Patricia Almeida Carvalho (Sintef AS) – “Assessing the stability of novel tetrahedrites produced by powder metallurgy” + Q&A

16:50 - End of webinar

The event was well attended, as 64 registered and 38 finally attended. This allowed to further expand the START’s mailing list, as some new names were appended to it. The full footage of the webinar is available on START’s YouTube channel¹⁶.

The screenshot displays a Zoom webinar interface. The main content area features a slide with the START logo and project information (Project: 101058632, HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01, Co-funded by the European Union). The slide title is "Extensive experimental campaign" and the objective is "To identify the most performing Tetrahedrite composition". It lists several properties to be investigated: Natural Occurring Doping Elements in the Mineral Concentrate, Phase formation, Thermal properties, Electrical properties, and Phase stability. A quaternary space diagram is shown with vertices labeled Cu, Ni, Zn, and Fe, and the chemical formula $\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{Cu,Ni,Fe,Zn})_2\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$. The right sidebar shows the "Audio & Video" section with a video of Serena Busatto, a "Participants" list including Bruno Vicenzi and B V, and a "Chat" section with a message: "Thanks for joining! We will have a Questions&Answers time at the end of each presentation. All participants will be able to speak, but please first announce your question here in the chat so that we are aware, thanks!".

Figure 48: A moment of the START Webinar #4, held on 14th March 2024.

¹⁶ https://youtu.be/YwHZ_J9PrbA

The screenshot displays a Zoom webinar interface. The main content area shows a slide titled "TEM" with the chemical formula $(\text{Cu}_{10}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{NiZn}_{0.5})\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_{13}$. The slide contains two images: a transmission electron micrograph (TEM) on the left and a corresponding elemental map on the right. The TEM image shows a dark, granular material with a scale bar of 20 nm. The elemental map shows a color-coded distribution of elements, with a scale bar of 10 nm. Below the images, there is a disclaimer: "Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them." The Zoom interface includes a top bar with the START logo and ID: 668-011-373. On the right side, there is a video feed of a participant named "patricia", a participants list showing "HOST (1)" Bruno Vicenzi and "PRESENTER (5)" B V, and a chat window with a message: "process accordingly. In case you do not have the powder, we can also help and mix it in our R&D center. If it is interesting for you please send me more details about your idea by using my email address: Damian.Karpowicz@genicore.pl".

Figure 49: A moment of the START Webinar #4, held on 14th March 2024.

6.2.6 ASGMI General Assembly, 8-12 April 2024

From 8th-12th April 2024, the ASGMI General Assembly was held in the city of Pachuca de Soto, Mexico. The activity of the different ASGMI groups of experts was overviewed and discussed, and information about the status of the START project was given in the presentation about the annual activities of the ASGMI expert groups.

Figure 50: In this image, Gracia Olivenza from ASGMI is giving her talk about the activities of the expert groups, where she mentions the participation of the expert group on mining environmental liabilities within the START project.

6.2.7 *Materials Research Society Conference, 22-26 April 2024*

RGS has also promoted the project (including the website link) at the MRS Spring Meeting and Exhibit¹⁷ in Seattle on 25th April 2024. The presentation “Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective”¹⁸ made by A. Ray (Figure 51) was well received by thermoelectric experts from all around the world with around 40-50 audience members.

¹⁷ <https://www.mrs.org/meetings-events/spring-meetings-exhibits/2024-mrs-spring-meeting>

¹⁸ https://www.mrs.org/docs/default-source/meetings-events/spring-meetings/2024/2024-mrs-spring-meeting-abstract-program-3-28-2024.pdf?sfvrsn=d2ef1b09_4 , page 493.

Figure 51: A slide of the presentation given by A. Ray of RGS at the MRS Spring Meeting.

6.2.8 37th EPMA General Assembly, 16 May 2024

During the hybrid format 37th EPMA General Assembly, in the afternoon that is dedicated to guest presentations on several topics of interest to the participating EPMA members, S. Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia SpA) delivered a presentation titled "START approach to powder metallurgy: Advanced materials for energy harvesting". The audience was of about 30, considering attendees in presence and remotely connected.

Figure 52: Two moments of the START presentation given by S. Busatto at the 37th EPMA General Assembly.

6.3 EVENTS IN PREPARATION

The START project will be participating in several events throughout the coming months.

6.3.1 Conferences, Exhibitions, Workshops, Webinars

A START free Webinar #05 is being organised, to be held as a hybrid event during our upcoming Annual Meeting at SINTEF, in Oslo (Norway). This hybrid format allows the consortium to take part in person, and other participants, including consortium members that cannot be in Oslo, to take part remotely.

The webinar, titled “Thermoelectric devices and applications”, will take place on Friday 7th June 11:00-12:45. This is the provisional programme:

- 11:00 Welcome and introduction Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA)
- 11:00 Maarten den Heijer (RGS Developments) – “Thermoelectric Power Generation applications for Heavy industries and Combined Heat and Power”
- 11:30 Hao Yin (TEGnology) – “100% Green Power for IoT sensors and industrial applications from low-grade excessive heat”
- 12:00 Jean-Yves Escabasse (START’s Scientific Advisory Board member) – “Adding value to TEG design by Additive Manufacturing: illustration in STARTREC, a new HORIZON project”.
- 12:30 Q&A with all speakers
- 12:45 End of webinar

As always, the webinar will be totally free, but registration will be strictly required. Advertising has started (Figure 53) and registrations are underway.

Figure 53: An image used on the project website and the social media to advertise the 5th free webinar.

The START project will have a booth at the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30th June - 4th July). The ECT and ICT are regular events that were already highlighted in the Events List, and the occasion of having them coinciding in Europe could not be missed. Presentations will also be delivered in various sessions, in particular F. Neves (LNEG), our Coordinator, has been invited to speak in the session “Cu-based chalcogenides II”, planned for Thursday 4th July 11:30-13:00, and the title of his presentation will be “Tetrahedrite-based thermoelectrics: the START project's approach”. Furthermore, RGS has pushed for the establishment of an industrial session for thermoelectric application (“TE Industry”, planned as well on Thursday 4th July 09:00-11:00) where A. Ray will be presenting with a talk on “Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective”. The provisional

programme¹⁹ of the mentioned sessions is visible in Figure 55. Closer to the event, we are going to publish more information on the website and social media.

Figure 54: Logo of the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference (ICT/ECT 2024) in Krakow, Poland (30th June - 4th July).

¹⁹ <https://ict2024.agh.edu.pl/en/conference/preliminary-program>

THURSDAY, JULY 4, 2024			
	Large Hall A Session: TE Industry Chairman: Jean-Pierre FLEURIAL	Large Hall B Session: Zintl phases II Chairman: Franck GASCOIN	Medium Hall Session: Organic materials Chairman: Przemyslaw DATA
9:00-9:15	Guillaume SAVELLI, P. Faucherand <i>Chips thermal management by micro-thermoelectric sensors</i> (European Thermodynamics Ltd, UK)	Alexandra ZEVALKINK <i>Thermoelectric properties of layered AMX compounds with tunable vacancy concentrations and interlayer bonding</i>	S. Muhammad, D. Motta, M. Bonomo, E. Marchini, S. Carli, S. Caramori, C. Barolo, Andrea REALE <i>Deep eutectic solvents for thermoelectrochemical redox systems for waste-heat recovery applications</i>
9:15-9:30	Uttam GHOSHAL, K. Kollé, A. Stautzenberger, M. Koeltzer, J. Jamison <i>Large-Scale Integrated Microcooler Technology</i> (Sheetak Inc., USA)		Konosuke OCHI, Ryota MIYAKE, Yuki HANAMURA, Hirokazu TADA <i>Thermoelectric Properties of Ionic Liquids</i>
9:30-9:45	R. Mohanraman, R. Lydiard, Richard S. TULEY <i>Device substrates: high performance with low thermal conductivity</i> (European Thermodynamics Ltd, UK)	S. Baranets, A. Ovchinnikov, Svilen BOBEV <i>Structural disorder in Zintl phases. The case of Yb₂₁Mn₄Sb₈ and Yb₁₀MnSb₅</i>	G. Calabrese, R. Cecchini, M. Ferri, F. Mancarella, D. Gentili, M. Cavallini, V. Morandi, Fabiola LISCIO <i>Enhancing Organic Thermoelectric Materials Through Local Control Wetting</i>
9:45-10:00	Alex GUREVICH, I. Steiner, Z. Dashevsky, S. Vitriuk <i>A High Performance Thermoelectric Modules with Substrates Made by Vapor Chamber Technology</i> (Double Check Ltd, Israel)	Amandine DUPARCHY, F. Kreps, E. Müller, J. de Boor <i>Unlocking the full potential of MgAgSb by unravelling the interrelation of phase constitution and thermoelectric properties</i>	Ting WU, X.-L. Shi, W.-D. Liu, S. Sun, Q. Liu, Z.-G. Chen <i>Dual Post-treatments Boost Thermoelectric Performance of PEDOT:PSS Films and Their Devices</i>
10:00-10:15	Aniruddha RAY, M. D. Heijer <i>Thermoelectric Modules and Applications: An Industrial Perspective</i> (RGS Development, Netherlands)	Longquan WANG, W. Zhang, S. Back, N. Kawamoto, D. H. Nguyen, T. Mori <i>High-performance Mg₂Sb₂-based thermoelectrics with increased structural ordering and microstructure evolution</i>	M. Betty LINCOLN, R. A. Sujatha, P. Veluswamy, H. Ikeda <i>Flexible polymer based textile thermoelectric generator for wearable human body energy harvesting</i>
10:15-10:30	Uttam GHOSHAL, D. Grimm, M. Koeltzer, J. Palomino, and J. Jamison <i>Multistage Conjoint Couples for Deep Cooling Applications</i>	Kejia LIU, C. Chen, H. Li, Y. Chen <i>Advancing thermoelectric performance in Nb₂C/Sb₂-based Zintl phase via the synergistic effect of Nb deficiency and dynamic doping</i>	Sanyin QU, Q. Xu, C. Ming, P. Qiu, X. Shi, L. Chen <i>High-performance n-type Te_{0.9}SiTe_{0.1}/PVDF/graphdiyne organic-inorganic flexible thermoelectric composites</i>
10:30-10:45	Charles BARRAH, A. Kiyabala Lopez, J. Siviter, A. Knox <i>Design of a multi-kW Thermoelectric Heat Pump</i> (Thermoelectric Conversion Systems Ltd, UK)	Santamaria Irene GARCIA, P. Ying, K. Nielsch <i>Improving the Thermoelectric Properties of α-MgAgSb through powder Atomic Layer Deposition</i>	Qihao ZHANG, L. Franke, M. I. Khan, Md. M. Mallick, U. Lemmer <i>3D Printing flexible thermoelectric devices for sustainable power generation and cooling</i>
10:45-11:00	Lech JERZY (Linseis Thermal Analysis Germany)	Miroslaw KRUSZEWSKI, K. Cymerman, J. Flaga, M. Chmielewski, D. Moszczyńska, Ł. Ciupiński <i>Co-based diffusion barrier for n- and p-type skutterudite-based thermoelectric materials obtained via pulse plasma sintering</i>	Szymon GOGOC, P. Data, K. Wojciechowski <i>Influence of acidic p-type dopant on thermoelectric properties of conducting polymers</i>
11:00-11:30	Coffee break		
	Large Hall A Session: TE systems Chairman: Jan KOENIG	Large Hall B Session: Cu-based chalcogenides II Chairman: Paz VAQUEIRO	Medium Hall C Session: Composites Chairman: Xanthippi ZIANNI
11:30-11:45	Daryoosh WASHAE, P. Bhatnagar, B. Baraieejad, A. R. Vazifeh <i>From Concept to Comfort: Complexities and Trade-offs in the Development of Functional Prototypes for Seamless Integration into Wearable Systems</i>	Filipe NEVES <i>Tetrahedrite-based thermoelectrics: the START project's approach</i>	Peter BALÁŽ, M. Rajčák, M. B. Hudáková, L. Kubišková, N. Daneu, P. Levinský, K. Križek, J. Hejtmanek, R. Džunda, M. Achimovičová, M. Baláž <i>Mechanochemistry in Preparation of Chatkalite/Stannite Nanocomposite: Kinetics of Synthesis and Thermoelectricity</i>
11:45-12:00	M. M. Maia, A. L. Pires, Andre M. PEREIRA <i>Wireless Energy Transfer using Photothermoelectric Devices</i>		Abinaya RENGARAJAN, M. Navaneethan, J. Archana <i>Enhanced charge transfer at zero-barrier injection of MoS₂/MoO₃ nanocomposites for thermoelectric applications</i>
12:00-12:15	David ASTRAIN, M. Araiz, L. Catalan, N. Pascual, P. Alegria <i>Electric production from fumaroles of volcanic origin in Antarctica by passive thermoelectric generators</i>	Xu LU <i>Manipulating Charge Carrier in Thermoelectric Sulfides</i>	Vijay VAIYAPURI, A. Jayaram, N. Mani <i>Boosting the thermoelectric performance of HMS/CNF composites via thermally activated conduction and microstructure engineering</i>
12:15-12:30		Yi-Xin ZHANG, Zhen-Hua Ge <i>Synergistically Optimized Thermoelectric Performance of Copper Sulfides via One-pot Modulation of the Second Phases and Cu Vacancies</i>	Huanfu CAI, R. Shi, J. Gao, L. Miao <i>Simultaneous optimization of power factor and thermal conductivity via charge transfer effect and enhanced scattering of phonons in Si_{1-x}Ge_{2x}P_{1-x}/CoSi₂ composites</i>
12:30-12:45	Yi ZHOU, J. He, G. W. Ho <i>Towards sustainable heat harvesting and decarbonization via non-unity thermoelectrics</i>	Tian-Yu YANG, Y.-X. Zhang, Z.-H. Ge <i>Pseudopolymorphic Phase Engineering for Improved Thermoelectric Performance in Copper Sulfides</i>	Andrii BOICHUK, T. Boichuk, M. E. Changarath, M. Krečmarová, J. P. Martínez-Pastor, J. F. Sánchez-Royo <i>Novel 2D materials with tunable properties for thermoelectric application</i>
12:45-13:00	K. Liang, H. Yang, P. Zhao, L. Yin, C. Lin, X. Wu, F. Cao, Q. Zhang, Jun MAO <i>Characterizing the thermoelectric cooling performance across a broad temperature range</i>	Oliver OECKLER, T. K. C. Alves, A. P. Gonçalves, M. Grauer, E. B. Lopes, M. Moslemi <i>Thermoelectric properties and crystal structures of tetrahedrite-type materials alloyed with Fe, Mn and In</i>	Van Quang Nguyen, Thi Huong Nguyen, Cheng Chang, Li-dong Zhao, JongHo Park, Jae Ki Lee, Su-dong Park, Sunglae CHO <i>SnSe-SnSe₂ & Bi₂Se₃-Sb₂Se₃ Misfit Layered Composite Crystal: Growth and Thermoelectric Properties</i>

Figure 55: Provisional programme (consulted on 17/05/2024) of the ICT/ECT 2024 for Thursday 4th July 2024, with the presentations related to the START project highlighted in the red rectangles.

The IGME team will present a communication titled "Transforming mining liabilities into energy assets. The case of the START project" at the "Congreso Geológico de España 2024" in Avila, Spain (2nd – 6th July). This presentation will introduce the project and focus on activities carried out in Spain.

Figure 56: Logo of the Congreso Geológico de España 2024 in Avila, Spain (2nd – 6th July).

We are also planning to organise a specific event later in the summer, namely at the end of September, most likely in Copenhagen (Denmark), with the collaboration of TEGnology. It will have the format of a one-day "Industrial Workshop" inviting companies that are interested in the application of thermoelectrics for their processes and devices. It is going to be organised as result of our clustering activities with the project THERMOS (TEGnology is a partner in both projects) and will be useful also for the exploitation activities of WP7. More details in the relevant chapter under Clustering.

As usual, a START booth will be present at the Euro PM2024 European Powder Metallurgy Congress & Exhibition in Malmö, Sweden (29th September - 2nd October). Project materials will be available for visitors.

Figure 57: Logo of the Euro PM2024 European Powder Metallurgy Congress & Exhibition in Malmö, Sweden (29th September - 2nd October).

Later in 2024, we also want to take a more active role in the Raw Materials Week (November, Brussels), and might propose a side event there.

Other smaller events where project partners will bring information and short presentations about the project will surely be attended.

6.3.2 Training Activities:

These will be better explained in D6.8, that is being submitted in parallel with this deliverable, but we report them here as well.

- During the EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School in Alessandria, Italy (15th - 19th July), H. Yin (TEGnology) will demonstrate thermoelectric devices for waste heat harvesting and other applications. Additionally, B. Vicenzi of EPMA will provide a project overview in the opening speech.
- A training course for Master students interested in the project, organised by ASGMI, is being planned for September 2024. This course aims to raise awareness of the START project among students. Experts from geological surveys and universities will participate. The workshop will be held in English from 25th Sept to 3rd Oct 2024 for a total of about 10 hours.

6.4 PUBLICATIONS

In the first months of the project, as documented in Deliverables D6.3, D6.4 and D6.6, a few documents had already been produced for publication.

Publications that have been uploaded on the website and on the Zenodo open access repository, where a “community” named “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling” was created, obtained a specific DOI, and they have automatically been added in the Continuous Reporting Publications page in the Funding & Tender portal for the project (see chapter 5.8.3).

In addition to this, a publication on a magazine, as reported in the following chapters, has not been uploaded to Zenodo, yet it is fully readable online, with open access, in the magazine’s website.

6.4.1 EPMA newsletters

As already detailed in chapter 5.3, EPMA published many internal newsletters with details on START.

6.4.2 START on the Innovation News Network

An article written by the consortium, with contributions from F. Neves (LNEG) and B. Vicenzi (EPMA), was published on the website Innovations News Network²⁰ (see Figure 59 and the annex for the full article) on 12th March 2024²¹. This article will also be published in Issue 18 of their periodical magazine “The Innovation Platform”, which is Open Access and that is planned for 3rd June 2024. Another article is foreseen to be published on the INN website in 2025, and in Issue 24 of “The Innovation Platform” that should be available in December 2025. In addition to this, a START banner, linking to the START website, is being hosted on the INN website.

²⁰ <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/>

²¹ <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/the-start-project-transforming-mining-waste-into-waste-heat-recovery-materials/45204/>

According to INN's published statistics²², they got about 613k sessions and 1.03M in the last 6 months, mainly from Europe (37%), North America (30%), but also in the rest of the world. Thus, it seems to be a good way to expand communication (and some dissemination) beyond the usual boundaries of the communities where the START partners are more active, i.e., geology and powder metallurgy.

Figure 58: The START side banner published on Innovation News Network.

The START project: Transforming mining waste into waste heat recovery materials

Critical Raw Materials | 12th March 2024

© shutterstock/Rainbow06

Figure 59: The heading of the article published on Innovation News Network website²¹.

After a few months we will probably agree the reposting of the article on our website and on Zenodo. We will also get specific feedback on the page views and distribution of the magazine.

²² https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/wp-downloads/statistics/Innovation_Statistics_Web_225_15-04-2024_21-04-2024.pdf

7 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

This task's activities started officially in May 2023, but details have been given in D6.5 (May 2023) and are being given in D6.8 (May 2024), that are dedicated to the training activities. Nevertheless, some activities (EPMA Summer School and the training workshop being organised) have been mentioned elsewhere in this deliverable.

8 TASK 6.4: CLUSTERING

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: All; M03 to M48

The objective of the clustering activity, that constitutes task T6.4 and began at M03 and will continue for the whole project duration to end at M48, is building a comprehensive cluster for the dissemination of the project. The main idea is to create an effective strategy to identify similar and interesting projects and find synergies to create value, avoid duplications and strengthen and maximize the START project results impact.

Projects that share a common theme or address similar challenges can form a cluster initiative and deliver shared strategic outputs. Thus, START wants to enhance links and synergies with such projects and initiatives. ASGMI with the support of all partners is identifying the project coordinators of the selected projects & initiatives. Mapping the synergies among the different projects will maximize the impact and contribute to have a more efficient and strong European Innovation.

A database was created and has been updated during this period with interesting initiatives and projects and will be kept updated throughout the rest of the project. Some of the resources consulted to feed this database are the following:

- The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) for H2020 or Horizon Europe projects
- The EIT (including the KICs on Raw Materials, InnoEnergy & Climate KIC)
- The internal community (partners in the consortium and its members)

The links are being established by a series of online short meetings with the relevant Project Coordinators or key people and the START project coordinator and/or the Communication WP leader.

Key events and meetings are essential to identify and establish good connections: the people from the initiatives in the clustering database, likely belonging to the audience target Groups 2 and 3, but in some cases also from Group 1, will be invited to the relevant events organized by START (seminars, webinars, trainings, final event) ensuring dedicated time for networking and collaboration. Conversely, START consortium members participating to events are supposed to seek connections with all interesting stakeholders.

8.1 CLUSTERING STRATEGY

A clustering strategy has been designed in order to be implemented during the whole project duration. This strategy consists of two work lines: internal and external clustering:

8.1.1 *Internal clustering*

Consortium members are being contacted to identify projects, or other initiatives in which they are involved and/or are aware of, and check if they have common points and potential to establish synergies.

8.1.2 External clustering

The strategy for external clustering consists in contacting institutions and organizations that are not directly involved in the START project but work in similar or complementary themes.

These can be classified as explained in the next subchapters.

8.1.2.1 Key institutions and actors

Associations and big organizations directly or indirectly related to technical projects or other research initiatives are especially important because networks in which they are involved have a big potential for clustering with START project. They have a “helicopter view” of the activities done by their members and contacting them is a fast and easy way to reach a large number of potential projects.

Key people (outreach people and project leaders) in these organizations have been identified and contacted in order to schedule meetings between projects or Work Package leaders.

Clustering task and communication leaders of the project contacted key individuals at EIT Raw Materials, InnoEnergy KICs, and EuroGeoSurveys during the previous reporting period. Additionally, contact has been established and meetings held with other initiatives and organizations, which are detailed in the following sections.

8.1.2.1.1 ERHASE Cluster

As we already documented in D6.6, in October 2023 a meeting with the ERHASE Cluster initiative took place. The ERHASE Cluster is formed by three European Projects (FAST-SMART, SYMPHONY, InComEss) with the aim to address the technical scope areas within the context of energy harvesting and storage technologies. Through the cluster, participating projects may expand their impact beyond the project level, while contributing to the dissemination of state-of-the-art research and developments. Together, the 3 projects intended to boost awareness regarding the research outcomes and promote energy harvesting with relevant stakeholders, such as academia and industry.

After the meeting, START effectively joined ERHASE, and is now listed on the web page of the cluster as a partner project (Figure 60).

As a consequence, START was invited to present in the ERHASE session included in the InComEss Final Workshop, that happened online on 31st January 2024, free for registered users (the InComEss project ended on 29th February). Also, the other ERHASE projects FAST-SMART and SYMPHONY presented their state-of-the-art, whereas the full morning was dedicated to the final summary of InComEss activities and results. The programme of the ERHASE session was the following:

- 14:05 SYMPHONY Project, P(VDF-TrFE) based piezoelectric nanogenerators for energy autonomous sensor systems - Dr. Jonas Groten, Joanneum Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, SYMPHONY Project Coordinator
- 14:20 FAST-SMART Project, FAST and Nano-Enabled SMART Materials, Structures and Systems for Energy Harvesting - Prof. Yi Qin University of Strathclyde, FAST-SMART Project Coordinator, M. Rostagno, GAE Engineering, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager
- 14:35 START Project, Conversion of secondary mineral resources into value-added products for energy harvesting systems - Dr. Filipe Neves, LNEG – National Laboratory of Energy and Geology, START Project Coordinator
- 14:50 End of the event

The event attracted 58 participants. The full InComEss Workshop, including the ERHASE session, is available on YouTube²⁴.

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface with a presentation slide. The slide content is as follows:

2. Overview of the START project

START approach to address the replacement of telluride-based TE materials

Unique technological solution
START will transform **waste secondary sulphide materials** in sustainable high added-value components for **tellurium-free thermoelectric devices**.

Material	MIN (%)	SYN (%)	zT (at T)
p-type tetrahedrite (Left)	20%	80%	0.69 (364 °C)
p-type tetrahedrite (Right)	50%	50%	0.49 (362 °C)

The graph on the right plots ZT (0.0 to 1.5) against temperature (0 to 1000 K) for various materials: Bi-Te (p), Pb-Te (n), Sb-Te (n), Bi-Sb (p), Bi₂Te₃ (p), Bi₂Se₃ (p), and Bi₂Te₃ (n).

Figure 61: A moment of F. Neves presentation during the ERHASE session of the InComEss Final Workshop, 31st January 2024.

²³ <https://www.incomess-project.com/erhase-cluster>

²⁴ Part 1: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?t=226s&v=IX9pHdQpnJE> ; Part 2 (comprising the ERHASE session): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?t=30s&v=KwZqO16QGuw>

Since the three projects comprising ERHASE conclude in February, March (extended to September), and April 2024, it does not seem possible to organize other future joint initiatives. After internal discussions regarding continuing the cluster by incorporating other projects similar to START, our feeling is that it might be more useful to conceive a new cluster with some newly funded projects.

8.1.2.1.2 THERMOS

Another recent clustering pursued by START is the connection with the project THERMOS²⁵. This is the acronym for “Tellurium-Free Thermoelectric Modules by Interface Engineering”, and the project is especially related to the development of tellurium-free thermoelectric devices using alternative raw materials. The complete process chain in THERMOS uses scalable processing techniques from the synthesis of nanopowders by high energy ball-milling, compaction, to the assembly of TE devices. In contrast to commercial Bi₂Te₃ modules, the project consortium will develop modules free of the scarce element tellurium with higher performance. The n-type Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ and p-type MgAgSb semiconductors that contain abundant elements were selected for the THERMOS device. THERMOS is a 36-month project that began on 1st May 2022 (like START) and is coordinated by prof. Kornelius Nielsch of Leibniz Institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden. It was funded by the M-era.Net framework for a total grant of about 1.2 M€. The contact originated from the fact that TEGnology is a partner in both projects.

Figure 62: Cooperation, workflow and benefits within the THERMOS consortium.

Discussions with THERMOS have been quite interesting and led to the decision of sharing activities, for dissemination and communication and for exploitation, and also to actively exchange scientific information, yet maintaining the attention to IP issues. On 11th April 2024, a delegation of START met some of the THERMOS main partners in IFW Dresden, the THERMOS coordinator's premises (Figure 63). The exchange was very open and fruitful and is leading to practical

²⁵ <https://www.m-era.net/materipedia/2021/thermos>

collaboration in the very near future, increasing the chances for both projects of achieving the respective objectives, and overall, that thermoelectric solutions can be more universally accepted as viable routes for waste heat recovery in Europe.

Figure 63: The THERMOS-START meeting on 11/04/2023 set the basis for joint initiatives.

The first practical example will be the Industrial Workshop.

At the end of September, most likely in Copenhagen (Denmark), with the collaboration of TEGnology, a one-day Workshop, including presentations from START and THERMOS, discussions and networking opportunities, will be organised. The plan is inviting companies that are interested in the application of thermoelectrics for their processes and devices, but also selected academicians that can give interesting information. So, it will include the results of our both projects THERMOS and will be useful also for the exploitation activities. More details will be provided closer to the event.

Given the end of the project InComEss, and the upcoming end of the other projects of the ERHASE cluster, the attendants decided that START will pursue the creation of an aggregation with other projects like THERMOS, rather than to continue the ERHASE cluster.

One possible candidate is the project STARTREC, that will be one of the topics of the START free Webinar #05, and also another project including RGS is starting now. It is felt best to engage with these projects that will extend their duration after START and THERMOS are finished: such a cluster could be more useful than ERHASE in supporting START and especially its legacy activities.

8.1.2.2 Link with communication and dissemination activities

Project consortium members participation in technical or commercial big events, congress or other initiatives is interesting because this participation brings the opportunity to meet key people and find out new projects or initiatives related directly or indirectly with the project in order to stablish synergies.

To maximize the potential of clustering in these events, the clustering strategy builds a list of the events in which the consortium members are going to attend, identify potential organizations or key

participants in the event and suggest to the consortium members to contact them before and during the events to talk about related projects. This list is actually included in the Events List for Dissemination and the most interesting events for clustering are given a higher priority.

8.1.2.3 CORDIS

CORDIS provides information on all EU-supported R&D activities, including programs (Horizon Europe, H2020, FP7 and older), projects, results and publications so is an essential platform for looking for projects under same or similar calls and finding out the coordinator to establish contact.

8.1.2.4 Clustering Database

The database listing the clustering actions has been updated (see chapter 8.1.3).

This database includes data such as the name or organization, contact person, date of meeting and comments related to experiences exchanged in the meeting.

8.1.2.5 Invite key actors to project meetings

Project meeting or events (virtual and in person) are good opportunities for inviting key actors (project leaders, researchers or stakeholders) to disseminate the objectives and advances in the project and try to establish synergies and common dissemination actions. Some of these researchers have been invited as speakers in the webinars organized by the project and have contributed to their dissemination and diffusion:

- Webinar #05 (7th July 2024):
 - Jean-Yves Escabasse (CEA, START Scientific Advisory Board)
- Industrial Workshop (September 2024):
 - Co-organisation with THERMOS
 - Other speakers
 - Key industrial contacts
- Webinar #06 (Autumn 2024):
 - Presentation(s) from THERMOS

More experts will be invited to future events, also from the clusters and projects that we have been talking with.

8.1.3 *Clustering database*

As already mentioned, a clustering database has been created in order to achieve the objectives of the clustering strategy. The database is being updated with new organizations and projects and will remain active throughout the project.

At the moment, the database lists more than 40 projects that may have a connection with START. The key organizations and projects with which initial contact has been made or meetings have been held are included in the following table. As this deliverable is public, but the full list cannot be public for privacy issues, it is not shown here. Only stakeholder entities' names are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Key institutions and interesting related project identified for Clustering.

Organization	Meeting date	Projects	
EIT Raw Materials	16/11/2022	EuGeLi	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/eugeli/
		RIS-CuRE	RIS-CuRE: Zero waste recovery of copper tailings in the ESEE region - EIT RawMaterials
		BioLeach	BioLeach: Innovative Bio-treatment of RM - EIT RawMaterials
		INCO-Piles 2020	INCO-Piles-2020. International consortium to recover CRMs from stockpiles/tailings targeting RIS - EIT RawMaterials
EIT InnoEnergy	To be scheduled		
Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM	18/10/2023	THERMOS	https://www.m-era.net/materipedia/2021/thermos
Leibniz institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden (IFW)			
H2020 and Horizon Europe Projects			
FutuRaM	To be scheduled		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058522
FAST-SMART			https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862289
InComEss	ERHASE Cluster		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862597/es
Symphony			https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862095
STARTREC			
REESOURCE	To be scheduled		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138460

8.2 KEY EVENTS AND MEETINGS

During this period of the START project, the consortium members have participated in different events in which they have disseminated about the project, its main objectives and topics.

In these events, members have had the opportunity to seek connections with interesting stakeholders.

Main events, that have been described with more details in paragraph 6.2, are listed below:

- Environmental liabilities workshop in Criciúma (Santa Catarina, Brazil), 28th November - 1st December 2023
- “Latin America – Europe: Cooperation opportunities for a more sustainable raw materials industry. The EU-AISiCal project case” workshop in Brasilia (Brazil), 30th January - 1st February 2024
- START at the ERHASE session in the InComEss Final Workshop, 31st January 2024
- START at the Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada (PDAC) Convention in Toronto, Canada, 3rd - 6th March 2024
- ASGMI General Assembly. Pachuca del Soto (México), 8th 12th April 2024

9 TASK 6.5: FINAL EVENT

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: LNEG, All; M42 to M48

A final conference will be organised at the end of the project as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the four years of the project.

The conference will likely take place in Brussels.

The details of the event (type of event, audience, keynote speakers...) will be determined during the project (starting around M42).

The final conference will try to be organised back-to-back with another mayor relevant event to ensure as large attendance as possible.

This task is not active yet. Nothing to report.

10 ANNEX I – START NEWSLETTER – ISSUE #4 – APRIL 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11262179

BIANNUAL NEWSLETTER OF THE START PROJECT | ISSUE 4

RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future

EDITORIAL

Dear members of the START community, We are almost halfway through the project activities and what a journey this has been! The advances we have made together are nothing short of remarkable. This edition of our Newsletter is a testament to our collective dedication and the exciting progress we've achieved. The completion of our first Periodic Report marks a significant milestone, and the advancements in tetrahedrite mineral-based thermoelectric materials are not just promising—they're a leap towards a sustainable future.

We're excited to share updates on our ongoing activities, our synergistic collaborations with the EHRASE cluster and THERMOS project, and insightful technical information on thermoelectric generators. But that's not all, join us on the Consortium Tour, where this time SGUDS and IGME-CSIC take centre stage. Plus, don't miss the insightful interview with Doug Crane from our Scientific Advisory Board, whose expertise enriches our understanding of thermoelectrics.

This edition also features the fascinating adventures of Starty, exploring the practical uses of thermoelectric devices in a narrative that's both educational and engaging.

Looking ahead, we eagerly anticipate your visit to the START booth at the upcoming 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference, ICT/ECT 2024, in Krakow.

We hope this Newsletter serves not only as a source of information but also as an inspiration for continued excellence. Stay connected with us for more exciting updates from START on our website and social media channels.

(F. Neves)

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Figure 64: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-001.

STARTY - 4: TE DEVICES

#4 - TE Devices

HERE YOU HAVE A DIAGRAM OF ONE OF THE TE DEVICES. THEY CAN HAVE DIFFERENT SHAPES.

OK! BUT WHERE AND HOW ARE THESE DEVICES USED? HOW CAN I USE ONE OF THEM?

GOOD QUESTION! DUE TO HUMAN ACTIVITY, THERE ARE HEAT STREAMS REJECTED TO THE ENVIRONMENT IN THE FORM OF EXHAUSTS OR EFFLUENTS...

...AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE LEVELS.

HIGH	>400°C
MEDIUM	<400°C >100°C
LOW	<100°C

WASTED HEAT TEMPERATURE

Figure 65: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-002.

Figure 66: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-003.

Figure 67: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-004.

START CHRONICLES: GEOLOGY, THERMOELECTRICS AND MORE

NEWS FROM WORKPACKAGES

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 3 “Development of tetrahedrite mineral-based thermoelectric materials”

WP3 partners have synthesized (by High Energy Ball Milling, HEBM) and sintered (by Spark Plasma Sintering, SPS) more tetrahedrites samples at varying mineral/synthetic ratios, with the aim of incorporating the highest amount of mineral concentrate from mine tailings in the formulation of the TE compositions, but without compromising too much on the thermoelectric properties. The main results obtained with these samples have been summarized in the radar graph in Figure 1: thermoelectric (TE) properties (measured at 350 °C) are shown for samples prepared in the START project, and for a reference tetrahedrite sample¹, which has the highest reported ZT value among tetrahedrites made via the same synthesis process employed in the project (HEBM + SPS).

Figure 1 - Radar graph summarizing the TE properties of some representative START samples, measured at 350 °C. To help visualization, each axis goes from zero or from the value of minimum acceptability to the maximum value measured for each property, for this class of materials. Density (%) is the density of the sintered pellet with respect to the density of the powder material. Axes spans: (density (%): 80-100; Seebeck: 100- 250 ($\mu\text{V/K}$); Thermal resistivity: 0.5-3 ($\text{m}\cdot\text{K}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$); Electrical conductivity: 0-20 ($\text{mS}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$); ZT: 0-1. In general, a bigger area identifies a better performing TE material.

As can be observed from the graph:

- the synthetic tetrahedrite with optimized composition developed in the START project has higher ZT compared to the maximum value reported for HEBM+SPS samples (0.69 vs 0.61)
- the TE properties of the pure mineral are clearly inferior (possibly related to incomplete sintering)
- incorporating 20% of mineral concentrate in the tetrahedrite formulation yields a material with figure of merit comparable to the synthetic one (ZT = 0.72)
- incorporating 50% of mineral concentrate results in slightly decreased ZT (0.49).

While in the initial phase of the START project, the performance of a tetrahedrite sample was assessed solely based on the maximum ZT/PF reached at 350 °C (target range of working temperatures identified for the TEG devices is RT-350 °C), at this stage of the project, the thermal stability over time has been included as additional criterion to further refine the p-type materials composition. This evaluation is very important to obtain a material that can withstand the operational environment in which the final TEG will operate. For these experiments, the TE properties S (thermopower) and ρ (electrical resistivity) were measured at constant intervals over the course of four days, while the sample was kept at 350 °C in helium atmosphere. Thermal conductivity was measured at the beginning and at the end of the thermal treatment. Preliminary results evidenced a promising retention of TE properties over the investigated time period, confirming their suitability for the integration in the first implementation of a START-Thermoelectric Generator.

Next steps will be the evaluation of the effect of repeated thermal cycles on the thermoelectric properties, as the materials will be subject to multiple heating and cooling cycles at the working conditions. These effects will not only be assessed by measuring the TE properties, but also by performing temperature dependent XRD measurements and TEM microstructure analysis.

Since tetrahedrites are known to be sensitive to degradation if heated in a non-inert atmosphere (oxidation and sulphur loss at $T > 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), we are testing the use of protective coatings to “encapsulate” the p-type thermoelectric legs, and thus to overcome the thermal degradation of the device during actual operating conditions (see WP4). The first sintered and coated legs are almost ready now for the integration tests and assembly of the first START TE device. Updates on this in the next Newsletter, stay tuned!

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 4 “Assessment of thermoelectric materials”

The characterization of mineral and synthetic materials continues as a background activity of the whole project. New key results include the use of mass spectrometry to detect the formation of SO_2 gas in the materials during annealing, which is responsible for generation of porosity and loss of sulphur during device service (Figure 2). In addition, density functional theory provided a fundamental understanding of the role of iron in closing the band gap of tetrahedrite (Figure 3).

Figure 2 - SO_2 gas forms above $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the material produced by mechanical synthesis.

DFT-VASP Fe-doped $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$: $\text{Cu}_{11.0}\text{Fe}_{1.0}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$

Figure 3 - Iron introduces new electronic states in the band gap of tetrahedrite. Relaxed atomic structure, electronic band structure, and density of states of $\text{Cu}_{11.0}\text{Fe}_{1.0}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$. The blue, yellow, orange, and red spheres correspond to Cu, S, Sb and Fe atoms, respectively.

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 5

Model for the START TE module

In WP 5, RGS and SINTEF initiated the development of a comprehensive COMSOL model for the START module. This endeavour commenced with establishing a coupled thermal and electrical effect, initially utilizing temperature-dependent data for P-type tetrahedrite and N-type magnesium antimonide materials. To optimize the efficiency of these materials, the hot side temperature was set at $350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the cold side remained at $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. As material data became available from LNEG in WP 3 for synthetically produced tetrahedrite materials, they were seamlessly integrated into the model (example modelled scenario shown in Figure 4 (left, right)). Over the subsequent 6 months of modelling activities, the incorporation of n-type material data and the inclusion of heat interface (convection heat transfer on the hot and cold sides) will be prioritized to fine-tune the thermoelectric generator architecture, including fill factor and leg dimensions, to maximize power production from incoming heat flux density. Additionally, mechanical properties will be accounted for to assess the expected thermomechanical stresses in the module due to the varying coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the different materials.

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Figure 69: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-006.

Regarding the choice of materials for the general stack and required layers, a suitable candidate for the diffusion barrier layer for both tetrahedrite and magnesium antimonide has been selected. For bonding/brazing purposes, two nano/micro-structured silver sinter pastes have been procured. Initial tests were conducted to explore process optimization for sintering these silver pastes, using thin metal foils. Various parameters such as applied pressure, sintering atmosphere (argon/air), sintering temperature and time were tested. Successful bonds were achieved with both silver pastes, demonstrating electrical resistances down to 6 milliohms and minimal porosity (see Figure 5 (left)). Currently, shear testing of the optimized bonds is being carried out to get detailed images of the fracture surface and a value for the shear strength for these bonds.

Furthermore, initial designs for ceramic substrates with copper pads plated with silver have been developed (Figure 5 (right)), and a manufacturing partner has been identified for production. Over the next 6-9 months, TEG active material sintered discs from WP 3 will be coated with the diffusion barrier layer and subsequently sliced into pellets of tuned dimensions based on modelling outcomes before being bonded to these ceramic substrates for the first TEG module prototype.

Figure 4 - START module (left) temperature distribution and (right) generated voltage across single uncouple.

Figure 5 - (Left) Silver bonding microstructure; (Right) Ceramic substrates for START modules including electrode designs.

START LCA and LCC models

The work done so far within the scope of WP5 – Device production, validation and demonstration, accompanied by literature review and benchmark analysis, allowed the definition of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) models considerations that should be applied to the TEG to be developed in START project.

The preliminary goal & scope definition considers:

- i. The comparison between the TEG device developed in the project and conventional ones based in BiTe and PbTe for low and medium/high temperature applications, respectively;
- ii. The analysis will be referred to a TEG module (n-type and p-type legs, interconnect, ceramic plate);
- iii. The environmental impact and costs analysis will be performed to scenarios with/without waste heat recovery and to tailings recovered semiconductor materials versus synthetic based ones;
- iv. The proposed functional unit will be 1 kWh of generated electricity.

With the implementation of the methodology specific for the LCA inventory development, resulted as a preliminary evaluation, the following items for collection of data regarding the TEG life cycle inputs and outputs:

Inputs (materials):

- Sulphides tetrahedrite for p-type formulation (kg)
- Cleaning products, other reagents and consumables (kg)
- n-type component base material (kg)
- TEG components (alumina plates, cooper interconnectors, others) (kg)
- Cleaning fluids, adhesives, solder, other consumables (kg)
- Water consumption (kg or m³)
- Diesel consumption (kg or m³)

Inputs (energy consumption):

- Mining activities (extraction, concentration, purification) (kWh, MJ)
- p-type production (powder technology, rapid solidification, layer deposition, others) (kWh, MJ)
- n-type production (kWh, MJ)
- TEG assembly production (kWh, MJ)
- End-of-Life technology (kWh, MJ)

Outputs:

- Electricity produced by the TEG (kWh)
- Wastes, leachates (kg or m³)
- Air emissions (kg)

A combined analysis of LCA and LCC will focus on the determination of the best environmental strategies and the most cost-effective options. The expected lifetime of the TEG device is a very important indicator in the study. The LCC model will include capital, facility & management (operation and productivity) and disposal costs, and consider no maintenance costs for the TEG use stage, since this type of device has no moving parts.

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 7 “Preparing for the future”

Focus Groups and the Delphi method have been used to collect views and opinions from experts and stakeholders on the future of thermoelectricity in general, and of the START project in particular. These methods counted with the participation of internal and external experts from several areas of importance to START including thermoelectricity, renewable energies, powder metallurgy, geosciences and commercialization. While the Focus Groups were created to bring together experts and used to collect data through group interaction, the Delphi method was used to gather information from the experience and knowledge of the participants, driving their knowledge towards a consensus.

Three Focus Groups were held physically and online. Ten questions were posed to the participants:

1. What are the big uncertainties of Thermoelectrics (TE) and materials for TE value chains? What could happen that changes the value chain?
2. What kind of applications do you see as potential and promising based on TE materials? By which year do you think such application could reach the market?
3. Do you know of any ongoing research or new results related to TE? Do you know of any new trends in TE?
4. Do you believe that the future of TE could be based on tetrahedrites?
5. Would you be willing to pay more for a sustainable TE device? How much more?
6. Do you miss any elements from the START planned activities/focus?
7. What are your main doubts for the START approach?

8. What are the benefits that you expect that you could gain/use from the START project? Any commercial ones?
9. Who (companies, research groups, field of expertise, etc.) could be interested in the START technological approach?
10. Would the appearance of a new, more efficient material, hinder START from becoming commercialised? If yes, what could we plan/do for avoiding that?

The Delphi method was held online, where a series of statements and questions were introduced to participants. Based on experts’ opinions and views, qualitative and quantitative data is collected. An example of a statement used, and the respective statistics are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - Experts' views and opinions to the statement: "The application of thermoelectric devices to transform waste heat into energy is the future of renewable energy and circular economy".

Figure 71: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-008.

The responses highlight several perspectives on the role of thermoelectric (TE) devices in the future of renewable energy. Some believe TE will have a place in the family of renewable energies, with a focus on thermal energy harvesting for industrial digitalization. Suggested application areas include the combined use of waste heat for electric power and domestic heating, with low-grade heat harvesting using TE seen as a priority, aligned with EU targets for sustainable heavy industry. Concerns on the application of TE are about cost efficiency, sustainable manufacturing, and heat-to-electricity efficiency. TE devices are acknowledged as one option for converting waste heat into electricity, though their role is perceived as limited to specific niche applications. Overall, the potential contribution of TE to the energetic green transition is recognized, but there is an acknowledgement of the existence of other renewable energy technologies with higher efficiency rates, that might be more interesting than TE. The importance of utilizing waste heat, especially in the current context of substantial waste heat generation, is emphasized for clean energy and energy circularity.

Both the Focus Groups and Delphi method interactions showed that experts see the START approach as having great potential for current and future application, which can contribute to generate green energy. It also shows that is very important to define value chains, applications, commercialization strategies, better performance of TE devices and to having prototypes developed and tested in end-user applications. These physical and online exercises allowed the team to collect data that will prove essential in designing and implementing a commercialization and sustainability pathway for the START technology-based value chain. The next steps include developing an innovation, sustainability and commercialization strategy that can help the START project activities to reach the market with unique, sustainable thermoelectric devices.

START FIRST REPORTING PERIOD POSITIVELY ASSESSED

The START consortium ended its first formal Reporting Period towards the EU at the end of August 2023, covering the first 15 months of the project. For those not too familiar with Horizon Europe and in general with European projects, a Reporting Period is a period at the end of which, in addition to all reports (deliverables) that have to be given at the respective deadlines along the duration of the project, the partners have to put together a summary Periodic Report containing both the assessment of the technical work done and the costs incurred in that period. The experts nominated by the Commission check the quality of the work done, the correspondence with the expected objectives within the time frame, and the coherence of the costs declared with what had been priorly budgeted. The process takes some months, first to write the reports on the consortium side, and then on EU side to check the reports. A Project Review Meeting is also undertaken, where the experts and the EU Project Officer give their opinions on what they have received and discuss with the consortium about issues or improvements for the future.

Finally, we are happy to say that apart from some minor observations and clarifications requested, the first Periodic Report was accepted towards the end of last year, and the consortium already received the relevant part of the grant from Horizon Europe. Well done, START!

START WEBINAR #4: "POWDER TECHNOLOGY FOR TETRAHEDRITE P-TYPE SEMICONDUCTORS"

As you may remember, in 2023 we organised three free webinars, that took place in the first part of the year. There you could learn especially about our approach to the geology part of the activity, i.e. where to find tetrahedrite minerals, and how to collect and assess them.

In 2024 we planned to continue, and another free webinar, the fourth of the series, has been organised for the 14th of March, 15:00-16:50 CET. We titled it "Powder technology for tetrahedrite p-type semiconductors", and we invited three of our consortium members to report on what is being done to transform the tetrahedrite mineral into a suitable thermoelectric material, using the magic of powder metallurgy. This was the programme of the event:

14:45 - Participants admission

15:00 - Bruno Vicenzi (European Powder Metallurgy Association) and Filipe Neves (LNEG) – Welcome and introduction

15:05 - Serena Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia Spa) – "Mechano-chemical synthesis of thermoelectrically-optimized tetrahedrites from mine tailing" + Q&A

15:40 - Damian Karpowicz (GeniCore Sp. Z. o.o.) – "U-FAST – devices for SPS technology" + Q&A

16:15 - Patricia Almeida Carvalho (Sintef AS) – "Assessing the stability of novel tetrahedrites produced by powder metallurgy" + Q&A

16:50 - End of webinar

The event was well attended, with 64 registered (and many added to our project mailing list) and 38 attending. The full footage of the webinar is available on START's YouTube channel².

Figure 72: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-009.

START WEBINAR #5 - "Thermoelectric devices and applications"

To continue with the free webinar series, the next event will be again, like last year (webinar #3), organised in conjunction to our project Annual Assembly, that will take place in Oslo, at the SINTEF premises. This hybrid format allows the consortium to take part in person, and other participants, including consortium members that cannot be with us in Oslo, to take part remotely.

The webinar, titled "Thermoelectric devices and applications", will take place on Friday 7th June 11:00-12:45 CEST and this is the provisional programme:

11:00 - Welcome and introduction Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA)

11:00 - Maarten den Heijer (RGS Developments) – "Thermoelectric Power Generation applications for Heavy industries and Combined Heat and Power"

11:30 - Hao Yin (TEGnology) – "100% Green Power for IoT sensors and industrial applications from low-grade excessive heat"

12:00 - Jean-Yves Escabasse (START's Scientific Advisory Board member) – "Adding value to TEG design by Additive Manufacturing: illustration in STARTREC, a new HORIZON project"

12:30 - Q&A with all speakers

12:45 - End of webinar

Soon you will have more information on the event if you follow our website and our social media (LinkedIn and X, find all links in the Contacts section at the end of this newsletter). As always, the webinar will be totally free, but registration will be strictly required. Join us if you want to know more about thermoelectric devices and their applications!

START JOINS THE ERHASE CLUSTER

Clustering with similar projects and initiatives is one of the activities that START is taking seriously, to improve both dissemination and communication, and to have better chances for the future exploitation and better impact. When clustering is effective it is beneficial for all parties!

During the initial stages of the clustering activity, we came across an already existing cluster of EU projects, named ERHASE³. ERHASE stands for **EneRgy HARvesting for a Sustainable future** and the aim of the cluster is to address the technical scope areas within the context of energy harvesting and storage technologies. The ERHASE cluster was formed by 3 projects: FAST-SMART, SYMPHONY and InComEss.

The SYMPHONY project⁴ presents a novel energy harvesting platform designed to power wireless sensor nodes deployed in remote or challenging environments. This system utilizes a fully printed energy supply comprised of recyclable and non-toxic materials. These materials include the ferroelectric polymer P(VDF-TrFE), printable silicon-based rectifiers, redox polymer batteries, and cellulose-based supercapacitors.

The project focuses on developing cost-effective and scalable methods for printing these materials onto flexible films, subsequently integrating them with energy-efficient electronics and sensor technologies, and offers the potential to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions across various applications by, for instance:

- Extending the operational lifespan of wind turbines.
- Optimizing heating and cooling systems through enhanced presence and motion detection using smart floors.
- Minimizing energy consumption in e-bikes via remote monitoring of tire pressure.

The printability of the technology facilitates cost-effective integration into stretchable and flexible devices. This unlocks vast potential for implementation in a wide range of future Internet of Things (IoT) applications.

Figure 73: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-010.

The "PLUG AND FORGET" philosophy serves as the driving force behind FAST-SMART[®]. This initiative brings together leading universities, research centres, and industry experts specializing in materials science, solar panels, and transportation systems. The project's core objective is to significantly enhance the efficiency of harvesting ambient energy sources, such as light, heat, and mechanical vibrations. This captured energy can then be converted and utilized to power various devices, including sensors and solar panels. This process is known as energy harvesting, achieved through the implementation of specialized devices called energy harvesters, and offers significant environmental benefits by utilizing readily available natural energy sources that would otherwise be wasted. A critical challenge in current energy harvesting technology lies in the reliance on toxic materials, such as Lead, and strategically important materials classified as Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), like Titanium. These CRMs are often limited in European supply chains, creating vulnerabilities and dependence on external sources. The FAST-SMART project addresses this challenge by developing innovative energy harvesters that utilize novel materials. These materials will be free from harmful elements and readily available within Europe's mining portfolio. The project focuses on two key categories of energy harvesters: piezoelectric and thermoelectric. These devices will be rigorously tested in three application fields – railway track vibration detection sensors, solar panels, and hybrid engines. The project's scope extends beyond material innovation. It also aims to revolutionize the assembly process by implementing more efficient, low-energy consumption synthesis techniques coupled with faster assembly methods.

InComEss

The InComEss[®] project focused on developing efficient smart materials that combine energy harvesting and storage capabilities in a cost-efficient manner for the widespread implementation of the Internet of Things (IoT). These materials are based on advanced polymer composites and are designed to harvest electrical energy from readily available ambient sources. By demonstrating applicability in key sectors like structural health and vehicle monitoring across various industries such as aeronautics, automotive and building scenarios. InComEss aimed to unlock significant market potential. The project proposed a single/multi-source concept that can harvest ambient sources, such as mechanical energy and waste heat, and produce electricity with the aim of powering wireless sensor nodes (WSN) according to the use-case requirements. This concept realized the demonstration of Piezoelectric and Thermoelectric Energy Harvesting Systems (EHSs) for powering various sensors, including Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS, in aeronautics and building), and Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems sensors (in vehicles) and sensors monitoring through an IoT platform. InComEss prioritized the development of sustainable Energy Harvesting prototypes free of lead and rare-earth elements, and based on polymers for enhanced recyclability. The avoidance of hazardous materials and the implementation of low-cost processing routes will help to reduce the Green House Gas (GHG) emissions.

The goals of the ERHASE cluster are the usual objectives of clustering:

- Define a knowledge sharing framework around common goals.
- Increase the outreach of each project's activities and enhance the visibility of EU efforts towards energy harvesting and storage technologies.
- Enhance and rationalize communication and dissemination, and stakeholders engagement activities.
- Strengthen the relationship between EU-funded projects guidelines.

Having acknowledged the relevance of the cluster and the affinity to the objectives of our project, START decided to join this cluster and is now listed in the 4 present members.

Figure 74: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-011.

The connection already led to a common activity: on the occasion of the Final Workshop of the project InComEss⁷, that was held online, free for registered users, on 31st January 2024 (the project ended on 29th February), START was invited to join a special ERHASE session, where START, and also FAST-SMART and SYMPHONY, presented their state-of-the-art. The programme of the session, that came after a morning dedicated to the results of InComEss, was the following:

14:05 - SYMPHONY Project, P(VDF-TrFE) based piezoelectric nanogenerators for energy autonomous sensor systems - Dr. Jonas Groten, Joanneum Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, SYMPHONY Project Coordinator

14:20 - FAST-SMART Project, FAST and Nano-Enabled SMART Materials, Structures and Systems for Energy Harvesting - Prof. Yi Qin University of Strathclyde, FAST-SMART Project Coordinator, M. Rostagno, GAE Engineering, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager

14:35 - START Project, Conversion of secondary mineral resources into value-added products for energy harvesting systems - Dr. Filipe Neves, LNEG - National Laboratory of Energy and Geology, START Project Coordinator

14:50 - End of the event

The event attracted 58 participants. The full InComEss Workshop, including the ERHASE session, is available on YouTube⁸.

2. Overview of the START project

START approach to address the replacement of telluride-based TE materials

Unique technological solution
START will transform waste secondary sulphide materials in sustainable high added-value components for tellurium-free thermoelectric devices.

Material	MIN	80%
p-type tetrahedrite	20%	80%
Seebeck	196 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$	
Resistivity	58 $\mu\text{Ohm}/\text{m}$	
Power Factor	0.67 $\text{mW}/\text{m}^2\text{K}^2$	
Therm. Cond.	0.62 W/mK	
ZT: 0.69 (364 °C)		

Material	MIN	50%
p-type tetrahedrite	50% <td>50%</td>	50%
Seebeck	181 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$	
Resistivity	62 $\mu\text{Ohm}/\text{m}$	
Power Factor	0.53 $\text{mW}/\text{m}^2\text{K}^2$	
Therm. Cond.	0.59 W/mK	
ZT: 0.49 (362 °C)		

Graph: ZT vs Temperature (°C) for various materials including Bi₂Te₃, Bi₂Se₃, and p-type tetrahedrite.

Figure 7 - A moment of F. Neves presentation during the ERHASE session of the InComEss Final Workshop, 31st January 2024.

START COLLABORATES WITH THERMOS

Another recent clustering team-up pursued by START is the connection with the project THERMOS. This is the acronym for "Tellurium-Free Thermoelectric Modules by Interface Engineering", and as you can easily see the objectives quite converge with those of START. THERMOS is a 36-month project that began on 1st May 2022 (like START) and is coordinated by prof. Kornelius Nielsch of Leibniz Institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden. It was funded by the M-era.Net framework for a total grant of about 1.2 M€.

THERMOS targets the development of highly efficient thermoelectric (TE) modules based on nanograined Zintl-phase materials for solid-state cooling and conversion from heat to electricity. The complete process chain in THERMOS uses scalable processing techniques from the synthesis of nanopowders by high energy ball-milling, compaction, to the assembly of TE devices. In contrast to commercial Bi₂Te₃ modules, the project consortium will develop modules free of the scarce element tellurium with higher performance. The n-type Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ and p-type MgAgSb semiconductors that contain abundant elements were selected for the THERMOS device. The targets are a greatly enhanced heat-to-power conversion efficiency (η) of 8-9% in comparison to Bi₂Te₃ from 20 to 300 °C, and a TE cooling (ΔT) of ~60 to 70 °C that is competitive against Bi₂Te₃-based modules. The moderate price, abundance and non-toxicity of the elements constituting the Mg-based Zintl-phases materials in THERMOS make them ideal candidates to substitute the highly toxic and scarce Bi₂Te₃ and to boost their commercialization.

Figure 75: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-012.

Figure 8 - Potential applications of TE modules in various fields¹.

THERMOS innovation objectives are:

- (1) To develop high-performance Te-free TE materials through interface engineering by particle atomic layer deposition (pALD).
- (2) To assemble TE modules based on novel materials to improve η and cooling ΔT and to enhance the module robustness by ALD encapsulation.
- (3) To fabricate nanograined TE materials in scale towards the production of larger-area modules with a high number of legs ($n=16$ to 64).
- (4) To test the modules in real applications and to evaluate their whole life cycle in terms of production, operation in an application and recycling.

THERMOS envisioned results are:

- (1) Realize **a)** a $\eta \sim 8-9\%$ and **b)** a cooling $\Delta T > 60^\circ\text{C}$ with Te-free TE modules through interface engineering.
- (2) Robust modules to survive >5000 heat cycles while maintaining $>95\%$ relative efficiency in argon and in air with ALD protected layers.
- (3) Establish routines to fabricate high-quality Te-free TE powders on a $\sim\text{kg}$ scale per batch, and to assemble modules with 48 to 96 legs.
- (4) Test TE modules in real environments. Evaluate life cycle of modules in terms of production, operation in an application and recycling.

Figure 76: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-013.

THERMOS will address several application needs. Solid-state TE devices have no moving parts and can be operated for decades without maintenance. In the past, they have been used in noise-free solid-state refrigerators, military and space applications. Since 2000 the TE research has focused on waste-heat recovery from combustion engines, powering wireless sensors, mobile and medical applications, and on-spot cooling (Figure 8). The markets for TE devices are growing annually by 7%, especially in the areas of telecommunication and the Internet of Things (IoT). These applications require modules made of non-toxic elements with low costs and stable performance at high temperatures with zero maintenance (Figure 9).

The THERMOS project will have wide impact and several potential benefits. It will develop modules with an improved η to 9% and a notable cooling $\Delta T \sim 60$ °C that will outperform and replace conventional Bi₂Te₃ modules to enable new market opportunities upon the usage of sustainable materials. It will lay the foundations for patent application and production of a new generation of TE modules in Europe. The THERMOS concepts for the material synthesis, like interface engineering and the module encapsulation by ALD, are also critical for developing TE modules from other emerging materials like Heusler alloys. THERMOS will support the SME company TEGnology to enhance their portfolio of TE modules for a larger temperature range.

THERMOS started at **Technology Readiness Level TRL 2** with material synthesis and will reach TRL 6 with industrial involvement. TRL 3 had already been demonstrated by IFW for module development based on Zintl-phase materials.

Figure 9 - (left) Abundance (atom fraction) of the chemical elements in Earth's upper continental crust as a function of atomic number¹⁰. (right) Cost (\$/kg) of raw materials for the typical n- and p-type TE materials¹¹.

Figure 10 - Cooperation, workflow and benefits within the THERMOS consortium.

The THERMOS consortium is based on a high synergy between five partners from four countries. Starting on the left side in Figure 10, the anticipated workflow and collaboration frame is based on the design and synthesis of novel Se, Bi and Sb precursors for ALD (WP2). The BUREs group@UPce (Czech Republic) has ample experience with such fundamental organometallic research. The quality and effectiveness of the prepared precursors will be tested by the group of M. Knez@NanoGUNE (Spain). Initially in a static ALD reactor and, upon optimization, the process will be transferred to a fluidized bed ALD reactor to enable coating of powders (WP2 and WP3). NanoGUNE is highly active in thin film coatings, ALD and nano technologies and is fully competent to complete these tasks. The team of K. Nielsch@IFW (Germany) is crucial for the synthesis and investigation of thermoelectric powders (WP1) modified on the surface by ALD@NanoGUNE (WP3).

The overall strategy of the IFW-Dresden is bringing fundamental material research into applications in the areas of thermoelectric materials, superconductors and magnetic materials. Upon assembly and protective encapsulation of the developed TE modules (WP4 and WP5), their fabrication will be upscaled (WP6) with the aid of V. Pacheco@IFAM (Germany).

IFAM conducts fundamental and applied research for solution-oriented material and technology development with thermoelectric materials and modules as the most important research topics.

IFAM will be also responsible for the life-cycle analysis (LCA) and recycling of TE modules (WP8).

The team of H. Yin@TEGnology (Denmark) is essential for demonstrating the functionality of TE modules in a real environment and commercialization of the project outcomes, (WP7). TEGnology is one of the few companies in the EU that is dedicated to the design and manufacturing of thermoelectric generators with environmentally friendly and sustainable materials (and also a partner of START!).

In addition to the particular benefits of each partner (see above), the following four benefits are the most important for the consortium as a whole: (i) highly collaborative and world-class research to be performed with cutting-edge outcomes; (ii) mutual student and staff training; (iii) sharing equipment and expertise; (iv) environmentally friendly approach by replacing toxic commercially used materials.

Thus, at START and THERMOS we really believe that fruitful collaboration can be achieved, and meetings are planned between the relevant partners in the two projects, so that synergies can be made at any level, including the organisation of joint activities for dissemination. On 11th April, a delegation of START met some of the THERMOS main partners in IFW Dresden, the THERMOS coordinator's premises (Figure 11). The discussion was very fruitful and is leading to practical collaboration in the very near future, increasing the chances for both projects of achieving the respective objectives, and overall, that thermoelectric solutions can be more universally accepted as viable routes for waste heat recovery in Europe. We will keep you informed of the outcome of our discussions!

Figure 11 - The THERMOS-START meeting on 11/04/2023 set the basis for joint initiatives.

Figure 78: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-015.

START ARTICLE ON INNOVATION NEWS NETWORK

START has prepared an article that describes the project and its first results in the initial year and a half: the text, titled "The START project: Transforming mining waste into waste heat recovery materials" has been published by the website Innovation News Network¹², and will be also included in the next issue 18 of their magazine "The Innovation Platform", due on 3rd June. A banner about the project is also visible on the same website, with a link to the START website.

The START project: Transforming mining waste into waste heat recovery materials

Critical Raw Materials | 12th March 2024

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Figure 12 - Heading of the article published on Innovation News Network.

We believe that by this communication effort on such a platform the awareness about our project will spread well beyond the boundaries of our scientific and industrial communities (mainly in the mining, geology and powder metallurgy sectors). In fact, the INN website reaches a wide audience (the latest statistics available on the platform show about 1M total page views in the last 6 months, for instance).

We are also planning another publication in late 2025, with more focus on the results achieved by then.

Figure 79: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-016.

START DISSEMINATION EVENTS

[EU SuperCluster Lapland Conference in Rovaniemi \(Finland\)](#)

On October 30th and 31st, 2023, G. Olivenza from ASGMI gave a presentation about START titled “Reusing Secondary Mineral Resources for the Energy Transition: The Project START Example” at the European Union SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference in Rovaniemi, Finland. In this conference, she talked about the objectives of START, its benefits for the environment and contribution to the sustainable development goals. More than 140 participants attended the event, in which more than 20 EU projects related to innovation in the exploration and acquisition of mineral resources were presented. Discussions about sustainability, the environment and social acceptance took place in the same event.

[START at the EU Raw Materials Week in Brussels](#)

Like last year, we also showcased during the EU Raw Materials Week 2023, a yearly event gathering a wide range of stakeholders discussing policies and initiatives in the field of raw materials, providing an overview of ongoing EU activities in the sector.

We showed our introductory video, with the addition of the Starty comic (issue #2), and also a poster. Participants could thus watch and learn more about the project’s objectives and actions.

Figure 13 - START video displayed during the Raw Materials Week 2023.

[Environmental liabilities workshop in Criciúma \(Santa Catarina, Brazil\)](#)

An ASGMI passive liabilities workshop was held in the Brazilian city of Criciúma from November 28th to December 1st, 2023. The workshop consisted of three days of conferences¹³ about different topics related to mining environmental liabilities and their remediation in Ibero-America, and one day of field trip in which a mine was visited, as well as different points around the city of Criciúma where the effects of environmental liabilities could be seen. Furthermore, there were some points in the trip where these liabilities had been remediated using different methods.

The conferences treated topics such as the management of environmental liabilities in different Ibero-American countries; the extraction of mineral resources from tailings; the use of those tailings to make construction materials; the geochemical and mineralogical characterization of tailings; and proposals for risks evaluation methodologies.

Between the many conferences of the workshop, Dr. Fredy Guzmán (Mexican Geological Survey) and Dr. Cátia Prazeres (Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia) spoke about the START project and the contributions of the Mining Environmental Liabilities Expert Group of ASGMI to the Work Package 2 during their presentations.

Figure 14 - Attendees at the Mining Environmental Liabilities workshop held in Criciúma, Santa Catarina, (Brazil)

[“Latin America – Europe: Cooperation opportunities for a more sustainable raw materials industry. The EU-AISiCal project case” workshop in Brasilia \(Brazil\)](#)

The workshop “Latin America – Europe: Cooperation opportunities for a more sustainable raw materials industry. The EU-AISiCal project case”, held from 30th January to 1st February 2024 in Brasilia, was organized with the aim of discussing the main challenges faced by the Aluminium and other metallurgical industry throughout its value chain, from extraction to the production of final products. This event was arranged by ASGMI in order to promote the AISiCal project in which ASGMI participates.

Figure 80: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-017.

The workshop had the objective of establishing a dialogue among different social actors (industry, research, governance, and communities) to obtain answers to meet the growing demand for aluminium as a result of the energy transition, in a way that is sustainable while maintaining the industry's competitiveness and profitability, as well as social acceptance.

Between the many conferences that spoke about topics such as the status of raw materials in Ibero-America and Europe, the innovations in industry regarding raw materials and the use of modelling tools in innovation, Fredy Guzmán, from the Mexican Geological Survey (SGM) gave a talk in which he mentioned the START project and the innovations it represents.

Figure 15 - Fredy Guzmán, Head of Environmental Projects at the Mexican Geological Survey (SGM) and Chair of the Mine Environmental Liabilities Group of ASGMi giving his talk "Identification, characterization, and recovery of mining environmental liabilities" during the EU-AISiCaI workshop in Brasilia (Brazil).

Figure 16 - Attendees at the EU-AISiCaI workshop in Brasilia (Brazil).

START at the Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada (PDAC) Convention in Toronto, Canada, 3 - 6 March 2024.

The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention¹⁴ is the event of choice for the world's mineral industry and this year it had almost 27000 participants. Led by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), and under the motto "European Union for a sustainable future" (Figure 17), the European Union (EU) booth accommodated and promoted EU research and innovation projects under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes, among many other activities. START was one of the 13 projects (Semacret, Multiminer, Nexgen-Sims, Rotate, Digiecoquarry, m4mining, EIS, GREENPEG, S34I, Minel0, Vector, and Hephaestus) selected to join the EU booth at PDAC 2024 (Figure 18). Filipe Neves (LNEG) was the representative of the START project and during the first day of the convention it was possible to briefly present the project to Ms Marina Zanchi, Director of the HaDEA and Ms Katleen Engelbosch, Head of Department (Digital, Industry, and Space) at HaDEA (Figure 19). For the START project, the 4 days of PDAC2024 resulted in an excellent opportunity for networking and promoting START activities within the mineral exploration and mining community.

Figure 17 - EU booth at PDAC 2024.

Figure 18 - Projection of the START video in the Horizon Europe area of the EU booth.

Figure 18.b - START leaflets and booklets with all Starty comics were available at the EU booth.

Figure 19 - (Left), Filipe Neves (START project coordinator) with Ms. Marina Zanchi, Director of HaDEA (on the right), and Ms. Katleen Engelbosch, Head of Department (Digital, Industry and Space) at HaDEA (center). (Right), Group photo of representatives of the H2020 and HE projects with Ms. Marina Zanchi, Director of HaDEA and Ms. Katleen Engelbosch, Head of Department (Digital, Industry and Space) of HaDEA.

Figure 82: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-019.

ASGMI General Assembly, 8-12 April 2024

From 8th-12th April 2024, the ASGMI General Assembly was held in the city of Pachuca de Soto, Mexico. The activity of the different ASGMI groups of experts was overviewed and discussed, and information about the status of the START project was given in the presentation about the annual activities of the ASGMI expert groups.

FUTURE EVENTS

START is organizing participation in several more events in the next months.

In the afternoon of 16th May, during the EPMA General Assembly, that takes place in a hybrid format and gathers many members of the association, a presentation of Serena Busatto (MBN Nanomaterialia SpA) will be given, titled "START approach to powder metallurgy: Advanced materials for energy harvesting".

We are also planning to organise a specific event later in the summer, linked to our clustering activities and in the framework of our exploitation efforts, but we will have to come back to you via our website and social media, just be aware of that!

This year, START will be present with a project booth at some events.

**40th INTERNATIONAL & 20th EUROPEAN
CONFERENCE on THERMOELECTRICS**
June 30 - July 4, 2024, Krakow, POLAND

In June, we will take part in the 40th International and 20th European Thermoelectric Conference, ICT/ECT 2024, that will take place in Krakow, Poland, from 30th June to 4th July 2024. This is the main international event for thermoelectrics, and in addition to our booth there will also be presentations in several sessions, more info will be given on the website and social media in advance of the event. Meet us there if you are taking part as well!

The IGME team working on the START project will present an oral communication in the "Congreso Geológico de España 2024"¹⁵, which is held every four years. This year the host city is Avila and it will take place from the 2nd to 6th July. The title of the communication will be "Transformación de pasivos mineros en activos energéticos; El caso del proyecto START" ("Transforming mining liabilities into energy assets. The case of the START project"). The work introduces the project and deals with the specific activities carried out in Spain and the tetrahedrites sampled.

In the Euro PM2024 European Powder Metallurgy Congress & Exhibition, organised as usual by EPMA and taking place this year in Malmö (Sweden) from 29th September to 2nd October, a START booth will be present, with all materials about the project available for the visitors of the large PM community.

Other events are directly linked to our training activities.

In the yearly edition of the EPMA powder Metallurgy Summer School, that will be hosted in Alessandria (Italy) from 15th to 19th July, the trainees will be shown a small demonstration about thermoelectric devices. The demo will be brought to the School by TEGnology, one of the partners in the project, and Hao Yin will explain how these devices can be used for waste heat harvesting and other applications. In addition to this, B. Vicenzi of EPMA will, as usual, give some basic info about the project in the initial speech of the school.

Moreover, in September 2024, a training course for Master students interested in the topic will be run as part of the START communication and dissemination work. The objective of this training is to give the START project and the work that is being carried out a greater visibility within a community of students. Different experts from geological surveys involved in project and universities will participate in it. The workshop will last approximately 10 hours divided in 5 days and will be celebrated in English. The organization of this event is currently underway; therefore, the exact dates are yet to be defined.

More events might see START participating in addition to these, and we will inform you in due time.

If you are from a similar initiative or project and would like to organise something together, please contact us!

Figure 83: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-020.

TECHNICAL PILLS

Some useful information that covers topics that are linked to our project! In this issue, we deal with the applications of thermoelectric generators.

APPLICATIONS OF THERMOELECTRIC GENERATORS (TEG)

Applications in heavy industry

The combined recovery of power and steam in European heavy industry aims to significantly reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions through the implementation of innovative technologies. Recent estimates reveal that industrial processes account for 26% of European primary energy usage (3196 TWh) and 48% of final CO₂ emissions. Additionally, about 29% of this energy is lost through effluents or exhausts, totalling around 920 TWh, with only approximately 304 TWh/year deemed recoverable. The START initiative focuses on high-temperature applications, targeting industrial clients that have high-temperature waste heat (>500 °C), particularly in energy-intensive sectors like primary and secondary steel and metals, glass, chemical, and cement industries. Notably, Iron and Steel (I&S) and Non-metallic Minerals (NMM) industries possess the highest share of such waste heat sources, offering a total usable heat reservoir of 123 TWh. RGS development has significant expertise in integrating TEG devices within these industries, as depicted in Figure 20. Beyond the electricity advantages, these applications also allow end-users to utilize concentrated heat as hot water in other areas of the facility, particularly valuable given the current surge in gas prices affecting industries.

Figure 20 - RGS Thermagy integrated in (Left) glass industry and (Right) in a typical steel plant.

Applications in μ CHP

Heating and cooling needs for residential, commercial, and industrial sectors constitute roughly half of the EU's energy consumption. Residential heating, comprising 16% of the total Primary Energy Supply (PES) at 17875 TWh, is currently supplied through collective infrastructures like gas or district heating grids, or via solid/liquid fuels such as biomass, which require no dedicated infrastructure for transport. Since 1990, biomass has seen a doubling in its role as an individual residential heating source, increasing primary energy supply from 265 TWh to 570 TWh, also reflected in final heat consumption. Given these widespread demands across Europe, the biomass-boiler market is experiencing significant growth, with increasing demands for enhanced performance and reliability. RGS holds a distinctive position in this global market as the sole industrial supplier of SiGe

TEGs, with the technical expertise to integrate them into commercial boilers using innovative system designs, as illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21 - (Left) TEG systems integrated into commercial boilers for CHP systems; (Right) Cylindrical TEG systems.

Applications in low-grade industrial waste heat

Waste/excessive heat from industrial manufacturing exceeds the amount of all renewable energy sources in total (Figure 22, top). While some part of the heat is reused for pre-heating or converted to power through Rankine Cycles, it is economically unprofitable to reuse this energy in other ways, due to the lower power density. It is especially difficult when the grade of the heat is low (temperature is below 250 °C or lower).

A thermoelectric generator is known to be robust, as there are no moving parts or chemical reactions. And in this temperature range, the instability of the thermoelectric materials and stress on the TEG modules are low/moderate. It makes large-scale energy harvesting from waste heat profitable, providing the TEGs themselves can be produced and implemented in very affordable prices. However, due to the limited efficiency in this temperature range, the output power is also moderate. It requires a thorough and holistic redesign of the material and module production.

Scale is the key for profitability. The Return of Investment of such applications has put stringent request on the selection of materials to be used. But in return, the big space and continuous heat availability might compensate for the low unit output. The inexpensive tetrahedrite materials from the START and a flexible module design (Flex-TEG, Figure 22, bottom) from TEGnology pave a new way of making large-scale thermal energy harvesting profitable.

Figure 22 - (Top) Amount of industrial excessive heating in compared to other renewable sources; (Bottom left) Applying Flex-TEG on large, curved surfaces; (Bottom right) Attaching Flex-TEG on pipes.

Figure 85: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-022.

MEET THE SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD MEMBERS: DOUG CRANE

In the last issue we have started to present you the members of our Scientific Advisory Board by short interviews where they highlight their activity and the activity of their institutions and companies. Today you will read about Doug Crane, who has been working for many years now in the industrial side of thermoelectrics in the US.

DTP THERMOELECTRICS

Figure 23 - Doug Crane works on thermoelectric technology development and the innovation and optimization of thermoelectric heat-to-power and thermal management. He is the Chief Technology Officer (CTO) of DTP Thermoelectrics. He served previously as Director of Thermoelectric Engineering at Alphabet Energy, Inc. and as Principal Engineer of Thermoelectric Systems/Development at Gentherm, Inc. (formerly Amerigon, Inc. and BSST LLC). He has over 25 patents and patent applications and has authored several book chapters and dozens of peer-reviewed papers and conference proceedings in the field of thermoelectrics. Doug was also the Principal Investigator for the U.S. Department of Energy's Automotive Waste Heat Recovery program at Gentherm, where he led a project team that included BMW, Ford and Tenneco. He holds a Bachelor of science in Mechanical Engineering from the University of California, Berkeley, and a Master of Science and Doctorate in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Maryland at College Park, where he studied the simulation of thermoelectric waste heat recovery from an automotive cooling system.

Doug, what raised your interest in thermoelectricity and what is your perception of the changes in the awareness of this technology outside the TE community along your career?

I first became aware of thermoelectrics in choosing a dissertation topic in graduate school. My dissertation was on thermoelectric waste heat recovery from an automotive cooling system. Unfortunately, I do not feel that there is much further knowledge of thermoelectrics now outside of the community.

Thermoelectrics does not have the general visibility of photovoltaics. I worked at Gentherm for 10 years. Gentherm's climate control seats provide heating and cooling to occupants and are in over 50 production vehicle models today. That said, I don't think that the general public really understands the technology behind the seats and these seats still tend to be in higher end models.

Figure 24 - A large TE generator by Alphabet Energy.

What achievements would you list as groundbreaking in the last decades, and what do you think would be the most needed breakthrough for a wider use of TE devices?

Considerable attention came to thermoelectrics in the early 2000s as a result of work from Rama, Harman, and Dresselhaus that showed the potential for higher ZT materials with higher potential conversion efficiencies. At Gentherm, our TEG design received recognition as one of the most promising technologies of the year in Car and Driver. Work by Poudel, Chen, and Ren at Boston College, MIT, and GMZ brought further attention to potential performance gains. Alphabet Energy and Phononic have raised significant funding and created considerable media attention. Higher efficiencies and effectiveness, lower cost, and improved manufacturing for higher cost effectiveness is still what is needed most in order to reach more markets as has been seen in photovoltaics.

Tetrahedrite (10.2 kg):
156 mm diameter
105 mm thick

Figure 25 - Large ingot of tetrahedrite thermoelectric material made by Alphabet Energy.

You have been working in programmes funded by the US Department of Energy: have you had the chance of understanding the main difference, and similarities, in the way innovation projects are funded in the US and in Europe? What regulations and incentives foster or hinder these projects?

Government funding in the US for thermoelectrics was more prevalent 10 – 15 years ago. Many of the program managers who championed such projects in the US are no longer in the same positions. It is very important to have government stakeholders with an interest in the technology to receive funding. In the past, emissions regulations and incentives relating to emissions reductions have been great motivators for the automotive companies to consider thermoelectric waste heat recovery and as such spurred interest in government funding. With further focus on electric vehicles with less opportunity for higher temperature waste heat recovery and previous difficulties reaching cost effectiveness goals, interest from the automotive sector has lessened.

Figure 26 - Alphabet Energy's power card and power card-y.

A question we already asked Jean-Yves in the previous newsletter:

how do you see thermoelectric devices in the rush towards energy efficiency and cleaner production? Do you foresee good opportunities in some sectors in the near future?

I believe that thermoelectrics will have a role in energy efficiency, cleaner production, and refrigerant-free thermal management.

The benefits of solid-state heat to electricity energy conversion can be unique in many applications. Until cost effectiveness increases, applications will remain niche.

You discover a working time machine and decide to jump to 2035. Are thermoelectric devices widely used by industry and society?

I believe that it is possible, especially with work such as that being done by START.

How do you see the development and implementation of START's thermoelectric devices based on tetrahedrites?

I see START's thermoelectric devices being implemented initially in niche applications for waste heat recovery where the cost effectiveness of the natural tetrahedrite recycled from mine waste can provide benefit on multiple fronts. I believe that START's devices can reach further applications as manufacturing continues to ramp up and cost effectiveness increases.

What led you to accept being in our Scientific Advisory Board? What are, in your view, START's strength and weaknesses?

I believe in tetrahedrite materials after having worked at Alphabet Energy.

I also was intrigued at the idea of using natural tetrahedrite from mine waste and the benefit of using waste materials to create waste heat recovery devices. The team is strong and diverse. The team might be strengthened further by eventually having an end-user member that really pulls the technology to a particular starting application.

Thanks Doug!

Figure 87: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-024.

CONSORTIUM TOUR

We continue our tour of consortium members: in this issue, meet SGUDS (Slovakia) and IGME-CSIC (Spain).

STATNY GEOLOGICKY USTAV DIONYZA STURA (SGUDS)

State Geological Institute of Dionýz Štúr, subordinated to the Ministry of Environment SR is a contributory organization which provides geological research and exploration at the territory of the Slovak Republic, creation of information system in geology as a component of the nation-wide information system, registration and evidence activities related to geological works performance, collecting, evidence and making available the geological works results carried out at the territory of the Slovak Republic, Central Geological Library performance, issuing and purchase of maps and professional geological publications.

The State Geological Institute is named after prominent geologist of the Slovak origin Dionýz Štúr. A proposal to establish an independent geological research institute in Slovakia was submitted in November 1938. The act on the State Geological Institute was approved by the Assembly on May 15, 1940, and on June, 12 of the same year the respective Governmental Directive was issued.

Figure 27 - Headquarters of the State Geological Institute of Dionýz Štúr in Mlynská dolina in Bratislava.

SGUDS role in the START project is to collect, identify and provide the required mineral materials for project partners for further research.

Figure 28 - First samples of tetrahedrite concentrate from Rožňava mine.

<https://www.geology.sk/>

AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS (CSIC)

The Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) is the largest public research institution in Spain and one of the most renowned institutions in the European Research Area (ERA). It is affiliated to the Ministry of Science and Innovation through the Secretary General for Research. IGME is the Spanish Geological and Mining institute, with 175 years of history. Since 2021, it is an institute embedded into CSIC.

The main mission of IGME is to provide the Public Administration, the Autonomous Regions Administrations and the general society, with precise knowledge and information regarding the Earth Sciences and related technologies for any development on the Spanish territory. The functions of IGME are: Studies, analysis and research in the field of Earth Sciences and Technologies, generation of basic scientific knowledge, technical-scientific assistance and advice to public administrations, economic agents and society in general, concerning geology, hydrogeology, geoenvironmental sciences, geological resources and minerals. The IGME develops interdisciplinary relations with other areas of knowledge, contributing to the best understanding of the territory and of the processes that form and modify it, to the sustainable use of its resources and the conservation of the geological and hydrogeological heritage.

The IGME team in START project is formed by Ester Boixereu (PI) Concepción Fernandez- Leyva, Ramón Jiménez, Paula Adánez and Jesús Reyes, who are part of the Department of Geological Resources for an Ecological Transition. The role of this team in the project is broad, as we participate in 5 of the 7 WPs of the project, although the activity has focused so far mainly on obtaining the tetrahydrate concentrates, contemplated in WP 2. Within the different packages the role of the IGME team is:

WP1: Coordination and management. In this work package, our main contribution has been the organisation, together with ASGMI, of the project meeting in Madrid, in May 2023.

WP2 Mine waste site selection, physical separation of minerals and concentration. To date, we have focused our activity on this work package, which is now close to completion. Firstly, we have been able to select 21 sites, a priori, with high tetrahydrate potential from our IGME Mineral Resources database. Following criteria such as % tetrahydrate, grain size and volume of mine waste facilities, this number was reduced. Sites have been selected from all over Spain in whose mine wastes there is a higher potential to find tetrahydrites. A total of 7 sites have been sampled, El Coriellu and Delfina Mines (Asturias), Peña Negra (León); Santísima Trinidad (Teruel), Santa Filomena (Cuenca), Lanteira (Granada) and Sierrecilla (Huelva). Mineral separation and concentration tests have been carried out on the samples in order to assess the best methods to obtain the purest tetrahydrate.

WP 4: Characterisation of materials. Work regarding this WP has just started. SEM analyses are being carried out and microprobe analyses are scheduled in the short term.

WP 6. Dissemination and communication. We have given several conferences and webinars to spread and disseminate the project learnings to date. These are: XV Congreso Internacional de Energía y Recursos Minerales (León, Spain, 22-24 November 2023), Science Week, Cu-AGSMI, XI Congreso Geológico de España (Ávila, Spain, 1-6 July 2024).

WP7: Innovation and exploitation strategy. We are making contacts with Spanish industries and companies.

<https://www.csic.es/>

Figure 89: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-026.

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²https://youtu.be/YwHZ_I9PrbA

³<https://www.incomess-project.com/erhase-cluster>

⁴<https://www.symphony-energy.eu/>

⁵<https://www.fast-smart.org/>

⁶<https://www.incomess-project.com/home>

⁷<https://www.incomess-project.com/news-1/recapping-the-incomess-final-workshop>

⁸Part 1: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?t=226s&v=IX9pHdQpnJE>; Part 2 (comprising the ERHASE session): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?t=30s&v=KwZgO16QGGuw>

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¹³<https://asgmi.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/00-Agenda-Taller-Pasivos-Ambientales-Mineros.pdf> (in Spanish)

¹⁴<https://www.pdac.ca/convention>

¹⁵<https://sociedadgeologica.org/congresos/xi-congreso-geologico-de-espana/>

CONTACTS

START regularly updates its website and social media with news about its activities, but also with more general documents and info on the topics of relevance for the project. Thermoelectricity, waste heat recovery, mine waste remining, sustainability, raw materials and critical raw materials, energy efficiency, and many others.

If you are interested in receiving this newsletter and other special news from the project directly in your mailbox, consider subscribing our mailing list on the website ("Contacts" page, "subscribe" section)! Clicking on the "Subscribe" button, you will fill a form generated by Brevo, our mailing system, and will subsequently receive an E-Mail to confirm your address. Your data will be treated and stored in accordance with the EU GDPR Regulation. And do not forget to follow all our social media accounts! Here is the list of the important links to click to reach our news:

Website: <https://www.start-heproject.com/>

Twitter: https://twitter.com/START_HEproject

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>

Twitch: https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjFhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>

SlideShare: <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

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Figure 90: START-Newsletter_Issue_4-page-027.

11 ANNEX II – START ARTICLE ON “INNOVATION NEWS NETWORK”

INNOVATION
NEWS NETWORK

GALVANIC
ENERGY | PUSHING THE BOUNDARIES
OF EXPLORATION

SCIENCE ENVIRONMENT ENERGY CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS TECHNOLOGY ELECTRIC VEHICLES NORTH AMERICA
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The START project: Transforming mining waste into waste heat recovery materials

Critical Raw Materials | 12th March 2024

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The START project aims to produce thermoelectric devices for waste heat recovery applications from secondary mineral resources (mining waste).

The START project is co-funded by the European Union (EU), Grant Agreement No 101058632, via its **Horizon Europe** programme, under the topic 'Building innovative value chains from raw materials to sustainable products' (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07).

It is a breakthrough project that aims to use secondary resources from mining waste and tailings to **develop sustainable tellurium-free thermoelectric (TE) devices**.

START approach and concept: Recovering heat from mining waste

The ultimate goal is to build an innovation ecosystem in the EU related to the production of TE devices with the highest economic efficiency suitable for use in waste heat recovery systems.

This represents an opportunity to efficiently use the EU's discarded secondary resources, reduce its waste and dependency on third countries, and offer a competitive solution for the sustainable development of renewable energy ecosystems using TE systems, in line with the strategies outlined in the European Green Deal and the EU Action Plans on Critical Raw Materials and Circular Economy.

A TE device is a solid-state energy converter made from several TE junctions electrically connected in series that consist of n- and p-type TE semiconductor materials (Fig. 1). It converts thermal energy into electrical energy. It possesses unique attributes: No moving

Figure 91: START article on “Innovation News Network”, part 1 (downloaded on 28th April 2024).

converts thermal energy into electrical energy. It possesses unique attributes: No moving parts, no maintenance, quiet operation, and absence of production of environmentally deleterious mining waste.

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of a thermoelectric device

Currently, most commercial TE devices use bismuth telluride (BiTe) or lead telluride (PbTe) as TE materials, which depend on the availability and price of tellurium. Considering, simultaneously, that China is responsible for around 60% of the world's tellurium production and the restrictive export policies it has recently adopted about certain raw materials, this dependence on tellurium-based materials becomes a huge disadvantage that hinders the large-scale implementation of TE technology in Europe.

To overcome this issue, START is proposing a solution based on the production of p-type materials that incorporate abundant sulphide minerals not currently in use, the tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral series, a copper antimony sulfosalt mineral, with generic formula $(Cu, Fe)_{12}(Sb, As)_4S_{13}$, which does not contain tellurium in its composition. These minerals are being collected in the respective European countries of the Geological Survey institutions included in the consortium.

The general concept of the START project is based on a 'waste material-waste heat to power' methodology (Fig. 2), which is the genesis of a completely new value chain linking secure European mineral resources and energy production. At the same time, it also contributes to the advancement of scientific knowledge and technological innovation in the field of thermoelectrics, as well as promoting a decarbonised society.

Fig. 2: START project concept based on 'waste material-waste heat to power' methodology

START outcomes

START will have many outcomes. By creating an innovative, flexible, scalable, adaptable mineral-derived value chain for TE devices based on raw materials that are readily available in Europe, START will create a new rapid-growth commercial ecosystem that will attract new stakeholders exploiting market opportunities for replication and market development.

In fact, this will be a new market opportunity for European mineral resources, converting discarded waste secondary sulphide materials available in Europe into useful and valuable

FEATURED TOPICS

Figure 92: START article on "Innovation News Network", part 2 (downloaded on 28th April 2024).

mineral resources, boosting EU competitiveness on raw materials through the recycling of such mining waste, fostering the transition to a greener society and economy through eco-innovation, and promoting energy security.

START impact

START strengthens and expands the European raw materials supply sector by replacing a key component of thermoelectric (TE) devices with new materials sourced within the EU. This will substantially contribute to the main expected impact of Cluster 4 ('Industrial leadership and increased autonomy in key strategic value chains') of the Horizon Europe Programme. It is then expected to impact several areas significantly, as explained below.

For the environment, START plans to reprocess sulphide-containing mining residues, thereby reducing the environmental impact of mining activities by remediating potential acid mine drainage while preventing the loss of valuable resources currently ending up in mine tailings.

START will address the sustainable supply of raw materials, securing a reliable supply of raw materials for green technologies and, more specifically, for TE applications, as it aims to replace the current TE materials (BiTe and PbTe) and produce tellurium-free TE devices based on tetrahedrite. This mineral in START is being sourced from European mining sites.

Regarding materials and technology innovation, START is using scalable and cost-effective methods for producing high-quality p-type tetrahedrite powder materials that will be assembled into the TE devices. The production of tetrahedrite powders by High-Energy Ball Milling has already been scaled up to pre-pilot capacity. Innovations in assembling TE modules for demonstration are also being adopted.

The goal of promoting the development of a sustainable society is pursued by several dissemination and communication activities about the project aims and topics to inform about the benefits and potential of the TE technology and the importance of ensuring secure, sustainable and competitive supply chains for green technologies in Europe. The project has also started a benchmark analysis of life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) studies to evaluate the environmental and economic impacts of its TE devices compared to conventional ones.

Thus, the START project also contributes to the UN Sustainable Development Goals 7 (affordable and clean energy), 9 (industry, innovation and infrastructure) and 11 (sustainable cities and communities) and to the implementation of the actions of the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials outlined in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Actions of the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials to which START contributes

START main achievements during the first 15 months

In accordance with the specific objectives planned, START already obtained some important results.

Concerning the objective of developing a resilient and sustainable raw materials supply chain for the TE technology, first of all, donor sites containing mineralogically suitable sulphide minerals for producing the p-type semiconductor thermoelement were identified in various historical European mines, based on: The volume of sulphides; the presence and content of tetrahedrite; and accessibility and logistical issues. Sampling protocol methodologies have

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technique, and accessibility and regional issues. Jumping protocol methodologies have been established that follow a scientifically sound approach to sample collection and subsequent treatment.

Based on this, several hundred kilograms of discarded mining waste sulphides were collected. Tetrahedrite-rich concentrates from these minerals were successfully processed via High Energy Ball Milling (HEBM) in a pre-pilot scale (300g batches) to produce kilogram-scale batches of mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type powder materials incorporating different amounts of synthetic material to adjust the composition. Spark Plasma Sintering subsequently achieves the production of mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type thermoelements. Work is progressing to optimise the composition, performance, and maximum amount of mineral concentrate that can be added to the initial mixture simultaneously. At the same time, a compatible n-type TE material was identified.

Based on simulated performances, two applications for the TE devices have been defined: Combined heat and power (CHP) and low-grade waste heat from heavy industry. Work is underway to assemble the first TE device of the START project.

To define the commercial ecosystem and business environment, a comprehensive analysis towards benchmarking the life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) studies to measure the environmental and economic performance of the TE devices has started. The first component of the prospective exercise, i.e., focus groups, was initiated to assess the market perspective and social acceptance. A first-round Delphi Survey was prepared.

Dissemination/communication activities were carried out, including the publication of a biannual project newsletter entitled 'RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future' (available on START's website), the organisation of three free webinars on project activities, whose videos are accessible on START's YouTube channel (more are being organised in 2024), and the multilingual comic storyboard 'Starty explains START', where Starty, a robot character, addresses and explains the project topics in an easily understandable way.

START consortium

Fig. 4: The START consortium

The START project is co-ordinated by LNEG, a Portuguese public research and development institution. It brings together a total of 15 partners (Fig. 4) from ten EU countries and one associated country, including: Six research organisations with strong knowledge of geology, materials science and renewable energies; seven SMEs that cover the entire supply chain from production to exploitation and ecological footprint assessment; and two non-profit international associations with a wide network of partners and stakeholders.

Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Please note, this article will also appear in the 18th edition of our quarterly publication.

Figure 94: START article on “Innovation News Network”, part 4 (downloaded on 28th April 2024).

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